

UNIVERSITI TEKNOLOGI MARA

**CUSTOMER SATISFACTION AND CUSTOMER
LOYALTY ON COURIER SERVICE QUALITY IN
MALAYSIA: A REVIEW OF POSLAJU**

ZULAZMI BIN ZAKIUDDIN

MSc

July 2021

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ZULAZMI BIN ZAKIUDDIN

Dissertation submitted in partial fulfillment
of the requirements for the degree of
Master of Science
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July 2021

CONFIRMATION BY PANEL OF EXAMINERS

I certify that a Panel of Examiners has met on 7th July 2021 to conduct the final examination of Zulazmi bin Zakiuddin on his Master of Science thesis entitled “Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty on Courier Service Quality in Malaysia: A Review of PosLaju” in accordance with Universiti Teknologi MARA Act 1976 (Akta 173). The Panel of Examiners recommends that the student be awarded the relevant degree. The Panel of Examiners was as follows:

Mazzini Muda, PhD
Senior Lecturer
Faculty of Business Management
Universiti Teknologi MARA
(Advisor)

Anizah Zainuddin, PhD
Associate Professor
Faculty of Business Management
Universiti Teknologi MARA
(Examiner)

Rozita Naina Mohamed, PhD
Associate Professor
Faculty of Business Management
Universiti Teknologi MARA
(Examiner)

**PROF DR ZUHAINA
HJ ZAKARIA**
Dean
Institute of Graduates Studies
Universiti Teknologi MARA
Date: 5th July 2021

AUTHOR'S DECLARATION

I declare that the work in this dissertation was carried out in accordance with the regulations of Universiti Teknologi MARA. It is original and is the results of my own work, unless otherwise indicated or acknowledged as referenced work. This thesis has not been submitted to any other academic institution or non-academic institution for any degree or qualification.

I, hereby, acknowledge that I have been supplied with the Academic Rules and Regulations for Post Graduate, Universiti Teknologi MARA, regulating the conduct of my study and research.

Name of Student : Zulazmi bin Zakiuddin
Student I.D. No. : 2019601548
Programme : Master of Customer Service Management
Faculty : Business Management
Dissertation Title : Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty on Courier
Service Quality in Malaysia: A Review of PosLaju

Signature of Student :

Date : July 2021

ABSTRACT

This paper intends to identify the customer satisfaction and customer loyalty on courier service quality in Malaysia based on a review of PosLaju. The service quality that the courier service provides has an adverse impact on the satisfaction that customers received. Customer loyalty on the use of the courier service depends on how satisfied the customers are with the service quality. This research uses the design theory of SERVQUAL that is usually used in service quality literature as the basic theory to study the consequence of service quality of PosLaju on customer satisfaction and customer loyalty. A comprehensive literature review is carried out from various sources to understand customer satisfaction, customer loyalty, service quality, tangibility, reliability, assurance, empathy, and responsiveness. Descriptive analysis, reliability test, Pearson Correlation Coefficient, and multivariate linear regression analysis method were used as a method of data analysis to interpret the results. A pilot study was conducted, and the results were tested for its reliability before distributing it to the respondents. The results obtained from this research could help PosLaju to have greater control over their SERVQUAL used in the courier service in order to gain customer satisfaction and customer loyalty.

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LIST OF SYMBOLS

Symbols

df	Degree of Freedom
n	Sample Size
B	Unstandardized Beta Value
β	Standardized Beta Value
r	Correlation Coefficient
R	Multiple Correlation Coefficient
R^2	Coefficient of Multiple Determination
p	Significance Level
X	Predictor
M	Mediator
Y	Outcome

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviations

CS	Customer Satisfaction
CL	Customer Loyalty
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
MCMC	Malaysian Communications and Multimedia Commission
MNC	Multinational Corporation
SME	Small Medium Enterprise
SERVQUAL	Service Quality

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Introduction

Service quality is becoming one of the service sector's most essential aspects. Service quality generally refers to a customer's comparison of service expectations related to a company's performance. A business with a high level of service quality is likely capable of meeting customer needs while remaining economically competitive in their respective industry (Jade, 2017). Customers nowadays are greatly concerned over the degree of service quality that they receive. This has led corporations or firms to pay extra attention to their level of service quality to achieve maximum customer satisfaction, which will result in consumer loyalty. However, depending merely on a good marketing strategy that focuses on reasonable price and promotion alone does not determine success in retaining its loyalty and satisfaction. The ever-growing competition and fierce rivalry have made service quality become one of the crucial criteria for any organization. Corporations that improve their service quality will ensure its sustainability and allow them to compete with their fierce competition in the market.

Service quality has become a significant concern for society over the years due to its impact on customer satisfaction and loyalty (Balaji, 2015). According to Mittal et al. (2015), delivering high-quality service is of great importance to improve long-term customer relationships in a competitive environment. Gladly (2018), the Customer Service Expectations Survey 2018 showed that 54% of customers decided based on customer service, and 19% found it to be the most significant decisive factor. Premium quality and, in particular, the quality of service are essential for improving profitability and reducing business costs (Alonso et al., 2015). Therefore, service quality was considered a multidimensional concept in which its essential characteristics must be measured to ensure customer satisfaction and loyalty.

Service quality is the most significant element of ensuring that customer's input is the provision of the most pleasing and most advantageous services in this competitive market. If a customer's satisfaction is achieved, then the customer's loyalty will also be

performed. In addition, a company would not exist if they do not have the support of their customer. The creation of customer satisfaction is essential to improve the number of customers. These two terms are very crucial in attaining company objectives. Therefore, the relationship between customer and company is the most significant relationship to achieve satisfaction and loyalty. The aim and purpose will be to look at how the relationship of service quality with customer satisfaction and loyalty leads to business success in the long term. This study overview will outline the background of the study, problem statement, research objectives, research questions and hypotheses, the significance of the study, and conclusion of the research.

1.2 Background of the Study

Courier service sectors are considered essential to all humans. There are so many courier service companies available in the present market, which seems crucial and creates competition in the industry. Postal and courier services are linked to the delivery of goods, packages, papers, letters, and printed materials according to Noordin et al. (2014). A courier service was created to provide a speedier and safer alternative to the conventional postal service, which had been the only means of delivery for so long. Traditional postal services are notorious for having long delivery periods and may incur costs if things are bulky or heavy. In this case, courier services are seen as the best option, and while somewhat more expensive than regular postage, they are more cost effective in ensuring timely deliveries. Furthermore, since the introduction of online shopping, courier services have grown in popularity.

Having the capacity to purchase big and multiple products from online sellers necessitated the use of specialized delivery systems that would allow customers to not only get their orders, but also allow online retailers to provide services such as next-day delivery. This can only be done with the help of a courier service. Courier services are the greatest option for individuals who work from home on a regular basis or only on occasion. It is critical for every organization to ensure that vital papers are delivered to the correct person in a secure and timely manner. To ensure that they meet their clients' needs, more delivery specialists are expanding out into comprehensive delivery services. When it comes to moving their most valuable goods, a great number of individuals rely on the expertise and security of a courier service.

PosLaju is one of the pioneer courier services in Malaysia, which was initiated by Pos Malaysia around 1986. Two years after its introduction, PosLaju started offering domestic courier service. Apparently, PosLaju was not the first local courier service. The earliest courier service in Malaysia was City-Link Express (M) Sdn Bhd which started its operations in 1979. Next was ABX Express in 1984 and Nationwide Express in 1985 (Roslan et al., 2015). DHL Express was the first foreign courier service provider that entered Malaysia in 1973 (Izzah et al., 2016). The impact of good service quality in relation to criteria of tangibility, reliability, assurance, empathy, and responsiveness will be a key factor in this study towards customer satisfaction and loyalty. Essentially, PosLaju has taken steps to improve its service quality. Thus, a mere examination of the relationship between service quality, satisfaction, and loyalty is insufficient. The most important aspect for PosLaju now is to gain a better insight into its improved service quality and measures to enhance the quality of its services.

PosLaju ultimate concern has been on the service being offered to fulfill the customers' needs. Customer's intention of continuing to use PosLaju service depends on the service they offer. Additionally, the customer tends to share their experiences with their peers. Many believe that price is the most crucial element of concern among the customers. However, the service quality provided by certain companies is the most significant concern in the courier service industry. Malaysian Communication and Multimedia Commission reported that 128 courier licenses were issued in 2017 than 112 in 2016, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Total Number of Courier Licenses 2001– 2018

Source: Malaysian Communications and Multimedia Commission (2018)

Malaysia can no longer rely on multinational corporations (MNCs) for manufacturing and marketing processes to drive innovation and integration into global networks. Strengthening Malaysia's entrepreneurial ecosystem is likely to enhance the innovation environment, which contributes to the economy. The surge in the number of Small and Medium Enterprise in Malaysia applying e-commerce practices seems a contributing factor to why the number of courier service providers increases. The courier service industry seems to contribute more to the digital economy nowadays. According to Ahmad et al. (2015), the parcel service, for instance, has generated remarkable growth in the last few years as a result of e-commerce platforms using online shopping worldwide. Recently more people and companies have found a way to buy and sell at their convenient time. This trend has shown that access to the internet is not a threat to the courier service industry but more advantageous to generate more business. According to Annual Report 2017/18 published by SME Corporation, SMEs contributed RM435.1 billion to the economy in 2017, with higher GDP growth of 7.2% against 5.2% in 2016. As a result, the contribution of SMEs to GDP stands at 37.1% in 2017, with overall employment at 66% and total exports at 17.3% (The Star Online, 2018).

Table 1: SME GDP and Overall GDP Growth by Economic Sector

Source: SMEinfo (2018)

	2016 SME GDP	2017 SME GDP	2017 Overall GDP
	Annual Growth (%)		
Agriculture	-1.9	7.3	7.2
Mining & Quarrying	8.2	8.9	1
Manufacturing	4.8	6.8	6
Construction	6.8	6.6	6.7
Services	6.5	7.3	6.2
TOTAL	5.2	7.2	5.9

A typical courier service delivery is outlined as sufficiently small to handle by one person while not using any particular instrument or equipment. Delivery is most typically same-day, next-day, or one-to-three-day attributable to the time-sensitive nature and content of the shipments, like biological substances, spare parts, and medical materials. Lovelock (1996) outlined the express parcel portion of the freight transport companies as a service "whose core product involves the speedy transportation and delivery of customers' packages, generally vary in size." The requirement differs between companies and countries. He additionally uses the term "time-definite logistics industry," during which info networks are equally vital because of the physical distribution networks of aircraft, trucks, sorting hubs, and sophisticated/high-tech warehouses. The firms functioning within the trade/industry distribute through their networks and use native subcontractors for pick-up and delivery. All in all, the company is highly equipment-intensive with flat rate dominating, and therefore the variable price and amount of transporting packages comparatively low (Lovelock, 1996).

Moving many thousands of shipments every day needs specific procedures to facilitate at affordable prices. Therefore, these little parcels have to be compelled to be combined into larger units depending on the routing and final destination. This procedure essentially defines how to parcel carriers operate. For instance, a standard parcel delivery service that uses merely road transport operates as follows. A courier usually picks up parcels with a pick-up van at the shipment's origin, and there will be many pick-ups before the vehicle returns to a hub or terminal. This can be the origin hub for the cargo/shipment. In the hub, the shipments are sorted by departing or outbound line haul truck. Once the loading is complete, the truck leaves for the succeeding hub or terminal within the parcel's route. There the truck will be unloaded

and, therefore, the parcels sorted once more. If this can be a destination hub, the parcels are sorted into courier vans for delivery. These typical steps of parcel delivery service are presented in Figure 2 (Li, 2002).

Figure 2: Typical Steps in Parcel Movement from Origin to Destination

The above Figure 2 represents movements by road transport only. When it comes to air transport, the steps are not significantly different. An air express shipment has all the same steps as its road counterpart. The only difference is the transport mode between the origin, intermediate, and destination hub. Instead of line hauls, the transitions between the hubs will be done by an airplane.

1.3 Problem Statement

The challenging world of the service industry has forced business and services to opt and convey its easiest service quality so that they may strive and pleased their customers. Thus, customers having always plan and important role in the long-term success of a business. In any service business, the satisfaction of using their service will directly influence their loyalty. The dynamism of the courier service industry in Malaysia has been important to the nation's economy to outreach society, respectively.

The high growth of e-commerce activities nowadays is creating a new set of business opportunities as well as challenges to the courier service. Due to the intense competition, Pos Malaysia understands that customers have more choice to choose from regardless of whether they are locally home-grown courier companies like City-Link Express, ABX Express, Nationwide Express or international courier service players such as DHL, CJ Century, an American global courier delivery service, FedEx and others. Service quality has thus become a pillar of growth for Pos Malaysia. Thus, PosLaju needs to improve its services to give the best services to the nations. Besides rapid advancement in information and technology, which may influence the courier service industry, PosLaju must ensure their provided service is aligned with the changes (Ninikas et al., 2014).

PosLaju's low service quality may have an impact on their customers' faith in their courier service provider. PosLaju must constantly endeavour to meet the requirements indicated in an extremely specific order in terms of quantity and quality upon delivery, as well as whether or not the box has been damaged in any way. Should any concerns be brought up too soon and handled incorrectly, it will lead to consumer discontent and a switch to the industry's opposite rivals (Ho et al., 2012). The ability of staff to distinguish regular clients is equally vital for being informed of various preferences, issue solving, and improving product knowledge, as well as delivering personalised attentions that will boost satisfaction and encourage future repurchases.

Improving the quality of service should be a continuous focus for courier service providers and should never refrain from increasingly proactive customer satisfaction by providing a better service. Courier services are now defined as logistical services which considered essential. Therefore, the logistics service quality models are applicable in the analysis and testing of the quality of the courier services. On that basis, most definitions of service quality focus attention on the fact that the service must satisfy consumer needs and expectations and is viewed as a disparity in the delivery of service and perceived customer service expectations (Otsetova, 2017). Thus, the relationship between service quality with customer satisfaction and loyalty received a lot of attention from researchers and practitioners due to their importance to the organization.

Customer satisfaction and customer loyalty have been considered as important components in service providers in order for a company to gain more market shares and

making more revenue. According to Njei (2018), a company must understand the needs and desires of customers to be able to meet them well. Initially, these two factors are important towards a business strategy that contributes to customer retention and repurchase desire. Noteworthy data on the best way to make customers further fulfilled in this way is an essential result to any company to succeed in their marketing plan (Kabu & Maharjan, 2017). Customer satisfaction and customer loyalty hence are very important and are positively related.

Indeed, providing a good quality of services not only to satisfy customer needs but to have a safe position in the market while competing with other rivals. Many occurrences have been seen in the past where companies blindly carried out a marketing promotion that only benefited their profitability in return but has failed to secure sustainability in their business, and in the end number of customers decreased (Ngo et al., 2016).

Malaysian Communications and Multimedia Commission received 1,370 complaints in 2018 concerning courier services. The number tripled compared to the previous year with 414 complaints. The top three complaints are late delivery (39%), poor service (28%), and lost items (16%), which constitutes 83% of all complaints received in 2018. The surge in complaints on late delivery to 540 complaints in 2018 (2017:100 complaints) was due to high volume of items need to be handled during peak seasons, leading to non-compliance with delivery service standard (Malaysian Communications and Multimedia Commission, 2018). Late delivery is one of the most challenging issues to manage, as shown in Figure 3 below. This is supported by a recent article from a local newspaper which concerned on late delivery by PosLaju (Noor, 2019).

Figure 3: Top Three Complaints Trend 2014 – 2018

Source: Malaysian Communications and Multimedia Commission (2018)

The previous study on creating sustainable competitive advantage through service innovation of PosLaju will be an added value to adapt in this research. Customer satisfaction and loyalty to the service provided by PosLaju will further strengthen the relevance of having a national courier service which is part of the business arm for Pos Malaysia Berhad, apart from competing with their rivals.

This study will investigate the current service quality that PosLaju is providing, the relationship of customer satisfaction and loyalty, analyses the challenges facing by the customer when engaging the service of PosLaju, and action should be adopted by PosLaju to overcome the problem facing by the customer which leads to service dissatisfaction.

1.4 Research Questions & Objectives

This study focuses on six research objectives with the respective research questions to be answered as follow.

1.4.1 Research Questions

- a) Is there a positive relationship between **tangibility** with customer satisfaction and customer loyalty?
- b) Is there a positive relationship between **reliability** with customer satisfaction and customer loyalty?
- c) Is there a positive relationship between **assurance** with customer satisfaction and customer loyalty?
- d) Is there a positive relationship between **empathy** with customer satisfaction and customer loyalty?
- e) Is there a positive relationship between **responsiveness** with customer satisfaction and customer loyalty?
- f) Is there a positive relationship between **customer satisfaction** and **customer loyalty**?

1.4.2 Research Objectives

- a) To analyze the relationship between **tangibility** with customer satisfaction and customer loyalty.
- b) To explore the relationship between **reliability** with customer satisfaction and customer loyalty.
- c) To examine the relationship between **assurance** with customer satisfaction and customer loyalty.
- d) To find out the relationship between **empathy** with customer satisfaction and customer loyalty.
- e) To determine the relationship between **responsiveness** with customer satisfaction and customer loyalty.
- f) To determine the relationship between **customer satisfaction** and **customer loyalty**.

1.5 Scope of Study

Pos Malaysia Berhad has a network of more than 1,000 touch points with a presence across the country, encompassing post offices, PosMini, PAM (Pos Automated Machines), Pos-on-Wheels & Go2U (mobile outlets), PosLaju outlets and service centers, PosLaju Kiosks, PosLaju EziBox, PosLaju Prepaid EziDrop, e-Commerce Hubs, PosLaju EziDrive-Thru, as well as postal and stamp agents, offering Malaysians the most extensive retail network.

PosLaju is one of Pos Malaysia Berhad strategic business units, connecting over 80% of populated areas across the country. It has the widest network coverage and the largest courier fleet in Malaysia. With the widest delivery network coverage that reaches practically every geographic area in Malaysia and its presence in strategic locations across the country, PosLaju provides better convenience and accessibility to link Malaysia as a whole and beyond.

This research will be conducted in Shah Alam, Selangor, which will take place in four PosLaju outlets. It will focus on customer satisfaction towards the service provided by PosLaju, and respondent involvement will be the one who is using the said service.

1.6 Significance of Research

The research is very significant as it highlights out the unseen relationship between customer satisfaction and customer loyalty on courier service quality in Malaysia. This research will be able to serve as a guideline for potential studies in the Malaysian courier service industry. From an organizational perspective, it hopes that Pos Malaysia Berhad will benefit from this research to improve on its customer satisfaction level, which will lead to gaining more customer loyalty. The conclusions and results published in this analysis will provide a more reliable scientific metric and a point of view to explain and determine customer experience with their service and further improve the current service. Pos Malaysia Berhad can also use the research to improve the quality of their services such as in the office of physical facilities, availability of equipment and human resources, the performance of the reliability and

capacity of the service they promised, responsiveness during the provision of prompt service, the assurance of trust and confidence among employees. In addition, the findings will also help Pos Malaysia Berhad to know more about the preference of courier service among consumers. Moreover, this will provide Pos Malaysia Berhad with empirical support as a reference guide for planning the efficiency and enhancement of service delivery strategies to create and deliver customer value to achieve customer satisfaction and loyalty. This research aims to use the design theory of SERVQUAL used in service quality literature as the basic theory in order to study the consequence of service quality of PosLaju on customer satisfaction and customer loyalty. The model aims to explain how PosLaju consumers assign dimensions of service quality such as tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, empathy, and assurance, which can influence their satisfaction and how this impacts customer loyalty. Top of all, this research will be able to demonstrate if the SERVQUAL model is applicable to determine the impact of PosLaju's on customer satisfaction and loyalty with their services.

1.7 Limitation of the Research

Throughout the progress of conducting this study, there is a various limitation that has been recognized and vital to be pointed out for the researchers to examine and be alert.

1.7.1 Sampling Size

This study was conducted only focusing on one prior location. This study focuses on the response from the respondents who are from Shah Alam only. As a result, these results cannot be generalized as a whole. Therefore, it is vital for other future research to conduct the study in other different locations to discover and get more data regarding the factors influencing e-commerce usage and its impact on shopping malls.

1.7.2 Questionnaire Design

The questionnaire is based on close-ended concept which required respondent to choose on the answer that is best to represents their thoughts and satisfaction level. Even though close-ended concept questionnaire is easy and convenient, it limits the researchers from gaining more in-depth understanding and thoughts from the findings.

1.7.3 Cost of Research

The research on this study has been limited by the cost of the research. The cost that was used to conduct this research was entirely on the researcher. There was no aid in terms of money for the researcher to carry out the survey questionnaire. The costs of printing, transportation, and other administrative cost were borne by the author in order to complete this study.

1.7.4 Scope of Research

The data collected from the survey is solely on the consumers' point of view and does not generalize the staff or people directly working in PosLaju. The data does not show the point of view from PosLaju itself and their view on consumer satisfaction. The survey could be bias which may cause inaccuracy in the results.

1.8 Definition of Key Term

Table 2: List of Key Term

No.	Key Term	Definition
1	Courier service	A way of sending item from sender to receiver which is faster and more secure alternative to the traditional mail service that had been the only delivery service for so long.
2	Customer Satisfaction	Overall assessment based on the total experience of purchasing and consuming goods or services over time (Khadka & Maharjan, 2017).
3	Customer Loyalty	A deeply held commitment to rebuild and re-patronize a preferred product or service in the future despite situational influences and marketing efforts having the potential to cause switching behaviors (Oliver, 1999).
4	Service Quality	Characterized perceived quality of service as "the degree and direction of discrepancy between the perceptions and expectations of customers" (Parasuraman et al., 1988).
5	Tangibility	Physical equipment, equipment, personnel and written materials appearance (Zeithaml et al., 1990).
6	Reliability	Ability to perform reliably and accurately the promised service (Zeithaml et al., 1990).
7	Responsiveness	Willingness to provide prompt service and assistance to customers (Zeithaml et al., 1990).
8	Assurance	The knowledge and courtesy of employees and their ability to inspire confidence and trust (Zeithaml et al., 1990).
9	Empathy	Caring, easy access, good communication, understanding of customers and individualized customer care (Zeithaml et al., 1990).

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW & RESEARCH FRAMEWORK

2.1 Introduction

In many ways, the courier services sector in Malaysia is rapidly developing. The Communications and Multimedia (C&M) business contributed 8%, or RM 135.7 billion, to Bursa Malaysia's overall market capitalization of RM 1,700.37 billion in 2018. In 2018, the postal and courier services, such as Pos Malaysia, contributed RM 2.41 billion in revenue to the C&M business (Malaysian Communication And Multimedia Commission, 2018). Nonetheless, Pos Malaysia has increased its courier business in the last five years, owing to the rising e-commerce trend. Pos Malaysia now has 116 courier service partners, including Poslaju, CityLink Express, J&T Express, GD Express, SKYNET, and DHL.

In the service sector, customers are the most powerful individuals. It is critical for organizations to establish strong customer connections, please consumers, and attract loyal customers. Customer satisfaction and loyalty in the service business give a lasting competitive advantage and distinction from competitors in today's competitive market.

Organizations are looking to develop and stay profitable by relying on these three factors. Customers are more likely to remain loyal and satisfied with a company if their service quality is good. It is also proposed that consumers who feel good quality service experience also tend to share their good experiences with others that contribute to an increased customer base and that these customers continue to become loyal customers (Wu et al., 2014). Dissatisfied customers, on the other hand, tend to share bad experiences with others on the poor quality of service, leading to reduced purchases and customer base (Jeun, S. T., & Park, 2018). Studies have suggested a correlation between the quality of service, customer satisfaction, and customer loyalty on this basis.

In this chapter, the researcher will cover literature review, development of research framework, and hypotheses development. Thus, the researcher has identified

published journals, articles, and books that will assist in investigating the theories and past research that are related to this study.

2.2 Literature Review

2.2.1 Customer Satisfaction

Customer satisfaction is defined as a customer's perception of the product or service and how the product or service has met the customer's needs and expectations (Nyadzayo & Khajehzadeh, 2016). In the field of research, multiple concepts of customer satisfaction have been proposed. Many ideas describe that customer satisfaction is linked to customer needs, where a customer will be happy until they feel satisfied with the product or service they are given (Alzaydi et al., 2018). Research by Kim (2017) also stated that customers often have expectations of a given product or service. A customer will expect the new product or service to meet his expectations after purchase. In today's competitive business, the satisfaction experienced by customers is important, which leads towards customer's intention to repurchase (Kaura et al., 2015). A marketing budget alone for a customer retention program will not succeed if the customer satisfaction level is low. In general understanding, the long-term of company success is customer satisfaction (Jones et al., 2014).

In today's competitive business, customer satisfaction is considered an important performance component in business strategy. In essence, customer satisfaction is the sense that customers get when they experience a service that meets or exceeds their expectations. According to Ismail and Yunan (2016), quality of service can perceive the level of customer satisfaction. It means that it relates positively to the quality of the services which are offered to the customer, either existing or potential. Usually, satisfied customers will have a higher tendency to buy again and purchase more. Besides buying more of the product or service, a satisfied customer will react as a network to exchange experiences and indirectly motivate others to follow. Therefore, it is essential for a company to manage customer satisfaction effectively. To be able to do this, a company needs a reliable and representative measure of satisfaction.

In past empirical studies found that emotional behavior is considered as a factor contributing to customer satisfaction. This is proven when study after study shown that emotions matter more than reason when it comes to customer satisfaction. According to a study carried out by Batra (2017), customers who are satisfied with a company's product or service can be classified into two groups which are emotionally satisfied and rationally satisfied. Emotionally satisfied customers provide a company with improved importance, such as by purchasing more products, investing more in the products/services, or remaining with the company more often (Kierczak, 2021). On the other hand, a rationally satisfied customer does not act separately from dissatisfied customers. Thus, positive emotion from customer's experience does influence customer's satisfaction (Gan, 2017). According to Akaegbu (2013), in his research as cited by Levyda (2017) has defined that dissatisfaction will lead to lower retention and referral rates which impact the profitability and growth in revenue of a company. This is because customer tends to talk about bad experiences than good experiences. Once a customer walks away due to dissatisfaction feeling, it will be difficult to change the perception (Steward, 2021).

Customer satisfaction is critical because it provides a metric that marketers and business owners can use to control and strengthen their operations. It is a necessary component in the service sector since it leads to client loyalty (Sze et al., 2012). Loyalty refers to when a customer buys or keeps a certain product model for a longer length of time and has a favourable attitude toward business and its dealings (Otsetova, 2017). Customers can be pleased until a competitor's service arrives, with a higher quality and lower pricing. They may have favourable opinions of a company but be dissatisfied with its services, and vice versa. This example shows the importance of corporations taking appropriate care of their consumers, as they are their primary source of revenue. Despite the fact that the industry was sprouting like mushrooms after rain, Malaysian courier services must compete in this industry because customers expect the most out of their time, money, and efforts. Despite the fact that guidelines for achieving maximum customer satisfaction were available, the courier services still struggled to meet it. To begin with, most courier services do not provide appropriate customer service, such as being pleasant, attentive, or respectful. Human factors, in some way, have an impact on consumer satisfaction (Chicu et al., 2019). Furthermore, selecting an appropriate courier service is critical. However, some individuals, particularly students,

are concerned about postal costs. If clients do not have expectations that match their payment, courier services that are unaware of this will receive negative ratings.

2.2.2 Customer Loyalty

In today's highly advance competitive business environment, the best approach in gaining business advantages is to increase customer satisfaction that will lead to customer loyalty. In research done by Stale (2021), customer loyalty is a measure of a customer's likeliness to do repeat business with a company or brand. It is the result of customer satisfaction, positive customer experiences, and the overall value of the goods or services a customer receives from a business. Stale (2021) also stated that by engaging them intellectually, emotionally, and spiritually, this differentiation serves to drive customer loyalty. Conferring to various scholars, customer loyalty is defined as a relationship between customer and supplier (Russo & Confente, 2017). The behavior of continually purchasing or consuming products or services from a provider disputes other favorable deals from a competitor can be interpreted as loyalty (Bernazzani, 2021). Loyalty is generally regarded as a long-term approach aimed at creating shared benefits for companies and customers at the same time (Rasheed, F. A., & Abadi, 2014). According to Srivastava and Rai (2014), loyalty is a psychological personality created by the customer's continued fulfillment, combined with a mental connection to the business supplier, which contributes to a willing and consistent connection with choice, sponsorship, and bonus.

Loyalty has a beneficial impact on every company's income share. In placing more emphasis, Yoo and Bai (2013) supported claimed that loyal customers are less likely to switch to a competitor's brand just because of price and other special promotions, bring in new customers through word-of-mouth, and are inexpensive to maintain. The power of word-of-mouth should never be taken lightly. This is because positive word-of-mouth increases reliability and decreases perceived risk. (Zeba & Ganguli, 2016).

A loyal customer has a high tendency to encourage others to buy the same service and think more than twice before changing their mind to buy other services (Chambers & Chambers, 2020). Customer loyalty is developed in one day, but through

customer-centered approaches that acknowledge customers' wants and needs to fulfill their desire (Firend, A. R., & Alvandi, 2015). In placing more emphasis, Budianto (2019) had explained that customer loyalty only exists in the long term if the suppliers make the customers feel that their lists are the number one priority.

Nurbasari and Harani (2018) note that loyal customers always show honest and high-quality feedback. Loyal customers always assist a company in improving its products and services by giving solicit feedback (Patel, 2021). Therefore, in today's challenging business a company feels that loyal customer is important for them to stay in the market when competing with same services and products. With loyal customers, companies can maximize their profits by reducing operation costs and acquisition expenses.

2.2.3 Service Quality

Service providers often seek to acknowledge the concerns of their external and internal customers. Their concern can be acknowledged by their review of the quality of product or service that they offer. As defined by Parasuraman et al. (1988), service quality is the evaluation of the customer's service by comparing its actual performance with its performance expectations. It can also refer to the disparity between consumer expectations in terms of quality and actual performance (Lumen Learning, 2018).

Parasuraman et al. (1988) identified five dimensions of service quality identified as SERVQUAL dimensions which include tangibles, reliability, assurance, empathy, and responsiveness. Tangible includes the presence of machinery, external structures, tools for contact, and personnel. This dimension extends into the organization's appearance and interior. This communicates value and transmits a company's image (Zeithaml et al., 2016). Reliability concerns the service's ability to deliver the promised service or deliver on its promises reliably and accurately (Zeithaml et al., 2016). According to Zeithaml et al. (2016), that reliability as a service quality dimension is critical as customers often want companies to communicate implicitly and fulfill their promises.

Responsiveness refers to the ability to provide prompt service and customer support (Zeithaml et al., 2016). It is involved attentively and efficiently with customer requests, complaints, and questions. A responsive organization often communicates with customers and how long it takes to deal with their problems or answer their questions (Zeithaml et al., 2016). Assurance relates to the courtesy and experience of the staff and their willingness to provide consumers with confidence and trust. Lastly, empathy refers to the caring and individualized attention provided by an organization to its customers. Empathy can be offered in several ways, such as knowing customers' name, their needs, and preferences (Arlen, 2018). While some other authors have criticized the SERVQUAL instrument (Mohd-Any et al., 2019), yet SERVQUAL is the most commonly used method of confirmatory factor analysis. SERVQUAL has thus proved to be a valid model used in different service organizations and industries to measure the quality of service (Wisniewski, 2012).

The rising demand for courier services has led to Malaysian Communications and Multimedia Commission (MCMC) to licenced 116 courier operators in Malaysia. This highlights the fact that both local and foreign firms have a strong presence in Malaysia because of the market's potential. The rising use of courier services brings with it a slew of benefits and possibilities, as well as a slew of new difficulties (Brightman, 2000). In today's competitive industry, every firm is working hard to give the finest services to its customers. As a result, service quality is critical at this point in order to fulfil consumer expectations.

2.3 Development of Research Framework

In this section, Figure 4 shows the conceptual research framework designed for this study. It focuses on how service quality dimensions affected customer satisfaction and customer loyalty in using PosLaju courier service. Through analyzing the relationship between the five dimensions of the SERVQUAL model, customer satisfaction, and customer loyalty, understanding the relationship between them should be extended. In this conceptual framework, service quality dimensions are independent variables, whereas customer satisfaction leads to customer loyalty as dependent variables.

Figure 4: Conceptual Research Framework

2.3.1 Tangibility

The tangibles dimension is a substantial determinant of service quality (Mei et al., 2018). According to Jamal and Naser (2002), the tangible of the service surrounding can have a noticeable effect on customer's affective response and their behavioral intention. Similarly, when customers assess a service, his/her impression of the physical surrounding comes first (Pantouvakis & Lympelopoulos, 2008). In the same vein, Markovic et al. (2011) stated that tangibles are more important for services with more tangible aspects. Courier services are different from ordinary mail services by features. According to Roslan et al. (2015), tangibility covers three areas which are assets, personnel, and availability. Assets are referred to physical instruments and operative means outlet's location and web sites while the personnel is referred to employees who generate the service and contribute to the control of courier service activities (Roslan et al., 2015). Availability is referred to any instruments that indicated the existence of service along the delivery process.

2.3.2 Reliability

Reliability is a way company services serve their function in the right condition without making any mistakes. It is the measure of the stability of company performance and how a company can be dependable (Choy, Ma & Koo, 2013). In the research of Omar et al. (2015), reliability is found to be one of the most important dimensions in this principle of service quality. They as a company must perform their best in order to

gain trust from customers. In this context of dimension, it is to measure whether the parcel reached the right place and its destination. According to Hennayake (2017), reliability is known as the ability of a company or organization to perform its service accurately and reliably as promised. In other words, reliability can be defined as the company's ability such as to send the customer's parcel, resolving problems, pricing, and service provision. In the perspective of courier service, reliability can be measured as the time taken to deliver in the form of package delivery and the number of times the parcel has reached the right location and final destination (Bryant, 2020).

2.3.3 Assurance

According to Ma et al. (2002), assurance shows the ability to deliver confidence and trust to their customers. The courier service must guarantee their employees were well trained and knowledgeable about their task. In research of Goh et al. (2013) indicated a skilled employee or worker would make sure their customer provides a good, kind, and fast response to their problem. Employees need to be polite in responding to complaints, questions, and feedback from the customer. This was because once customers were not happy and comfortable with the service provided by an employee, they decided to turn to other businesses and would not go back to the previous company to do business. Phiri and Mcwabe (2013), assurance is the most important aspect of SERVQUAL dimensions. This can be proved by the facts where customers choose to deal with people or companies they can trust. This dimension is needed to ensure customer satisfaction.

2.3.4 Empathy

Empathy is known as the delivery of customer care and individual attention (Siali et al., 2018). It includes communication between staff and customers, understanding the needs of customers, and accessing customers. In this point of dimension, it is stated that empathy is shown by the kind and individuality attention from a company to their customers (Felix, 2017). It includes the most important thing in any business nowadays, which is communication, understanding the customer needs, and access customers. Empathy is an additional benefit that consumers trust and confidence while at the same time increasing their loyalty. Employees should be fully involved with the customers in every situation. As a result, this is a way for the company

to care and make customers feel special and valued related to the empathy of service quality to ensure customers stay loyal.

2.3.5 Responsiveness

It can be defined as the willingness to help customers and provide prompt service (Gulc, 2017). In research, responsiveness is described as a company service provider's willingness to deliver quick service and willingness to help its customers solving problems, feedback, requests, and questions (Omar et al., 2016). In the context of courier service, this could mean the response given to their customers by a courier service provider. Customers would have negative perceptions if an employee had no reason to keep their customers waiting.

2.4 Hypothesis Development

H1a: There is positive relationship between **tangibility** with **customer satisfaction**

H1b: There is positive relationship between **tangibility** with **customer loyalty**

H2a: There is positive relationship between **reliability** with **customer satisfaction**

H2b: There is positive relationship between **reliability** with **customer loyalty**

H3a: There is positive relationship between **assurance** with **customer satisfaction**

H3b: There is positive relationship between **assurance** with **customer loyalty**

H4a: There is positive relationship between **empathy** with **customer satisfaction**

H4b: There is positive relationship between **empathy** with **customer loyalty**

H5a: There is positive relationship between **responsiveness** with **customer satisfaction**

H5b: There is positive relationship between **responsiveness** with **customer loyalty**

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

The method adopted by this research will be explained in this chapter. This chapter sets out the component involved in carrying out this research which includes a questionnaire, population frame, and sampling techniques. This chapter provides an explanation of the data collection and data analysis method adopted by the author.

3.2 Research Design

The first stage of the research process is to identify the impact of customer satisfaction and customer loyalty on the courier service quality of PosLaju in Malaysia. The author makes observations and reviews theoretical findings through previous studies and research published through means such as journal papers, articles, books, and browsing websites. The author was then able to find the purpose, goals, and study scope for this research.

The population for sampling and survey should be identified after deciding on the study's goal and goals. The purpose of this is to design questionnaires to collect data from the respondents. The methods of data collection include research papers, surveys, and questionnaires in this research. The research paper is to search for facts, general information on the subject, and so on. Surveys and questionnaires are intended to collect the related statistical data and information in order to meet the research objectives. In addition, for the reliability and readability of the questions, a pilot study should be conducted to avoid any unwanted random errors.

Finally, during the data analysis, the data collected undergoes a compilation and interpretation process to present the result in an easier and more understanding way. Data analysis includes qualitative data analysis through a descriptive method of statistics and quantitative data analysis through reliability and validity testing. Then, a conclusion is deduced and a recommendation for further improvement.

3.2.1 Type of Study

In this study, the researcher will be using an exploratory research design. It is the most appropriate design to find what is the actual thing that happens or to find new insights throughout the research. In other words, it is to clarify a certain problem or to know the precise nature of the problem or situation happens. As the proposed exploratory research design will be used for this study, the researcher will be able to look at whether independent variables will affect the dependent variables. The reasoning for choosing exploratory research design is to look at how the SERVQUAL dimension (tangibility, reliability, assurance, empathy, and responsiveness) will affect the dependent variables of customer satisfaction and customer loyalty. According to Quinlan et al., (2019), the exploratory research design is constructed to establish a relationship between variables to explain or highlight the situation or problem between variables.

The information gained is not specific and loose in the design of exploratory research. It also focuses on secondary or primary data in which such data can be interpreted formally or informally (Warnick, 2015). Hill and Brierley (2017) are saying that the term itself shows the new situation or phenomenon is to be explored in certain circumstances. In the case of PosLaju, which was introduced by Pos Malaysia Berhad in 1988 is considered a national courier service. Thus, this field of research needs to be explored further to see how PosLaju will somehow retain their customers to continue using their courier service. This research conducted using the exploratory design is because the number of customers using courier service is offered by PosLaju will be explained more in data collection methods, and it is secondary data. Johnston (2017) are claiming that secondary data refers to data collected by other organizations such as government agencies, records, or other organizations' publications for research purposes. The data of customers using courier service nationwide is collected for the past few years, and therefore the exploratory design is used in which the researcher concludes to be suitable for the research to be conducted.

3.2.2 Data Collection Method

Data requirement is the first consideration at the initial stage of the project. The findings for the research could be obtained by either primary sources or secondary sources, or both together. The application of these sources will depend entirely on the research scope and the availability of these data sources.

3.2.3 Primary Data

Primary data is data collected from first-hand sources by a researcher using methods such as surveys, interviews, or experiments. It displays specific latest raw information not subject to any interpretation or attributes derived from it. Data accuracy, reliability, and controllability are the main advantages of using primary data. Researchers use surveys, interviews, and direct observations to collect the data themselves. Collecting raw data, however, can consume a lot of time, can be expensive, cost-ineffective, and unmanageable. The time frame and feedback for obtaining desired data are uncertain, which can make it difficult to evaluate the findings.

The primary data obtained in this research is by using the questionnaire method. The advantage of a quantitative study is the structured procedure along with the formal questionnaire used will make it easier to quantify and generalize the data to a population. Since data will be collected from a large number of people (N=384), the administration process for a questionnaire is much quicker and efficient. Consequently, due to the restrictions in place pertaining to social distancing and restricted movement, the data will be collected online via Google forms.

3.2.4 Secondary Data

Secondary data is derived from sources that are established by third parties, such as journals, articles, conference proceedings, company reports, and case studies. The secondary data in this research is collected by reviewing those journal article publication and comparing it with the primary data collected through survey questionnaires. Furthermore, secondary data is easily obtainable through websites,

records, articles, and the likes, which are readily available. The disadvantage of using secondary data is the author cannot decide what is collected. The author can only hope that the data is of good quality.

3.2.5 Ethical Consideration in Data Collection

Ethics describe what is or is not legitimate or ethical to try and do. Codes of behavior and legal considerations in most countries can give some mounted rules and principles for researchers, and research ethics has a positive role to play within the style and conduct of human research, but it wants or needs to be seen as an integral part of the research method. Commonly control beliefs regarding research ethics embrace the importance of protecting vulnerable populations maintaining professional standards, safeguarding the rights and well-being of participants, risk management, and ensuring public support for research (Edwards & Skinner, 2009). Ethical concerns would like to be considered in each part of the research study, not just in the research style or once the researcher receives any needed ethical clearance and authorization to begin the research. The researcher desires to think about and touch on or act upon ethical responsibilities and concerns throughout a project, even beyond the information or data compilation section or phase into analysis, write up and publication (Edwards & Skinner, 2009). Furthermore, it is the right of individuals or firms to decline to participate in research due to some particular aspects. Therefore, it is crucial to describe the data collection, analysis, write-up, and publication to the participants and firms.

3.2.6 Sampling Design

The researcher will investigate five steps under the sampling design that determine the target population, the sampling frame and location, the sampling elements, the sampling techniques, and the sampling size of the respondents.

3.2.6.1 Target Population

The target population is the group of people who are interested in analyzing for research purposes to obtain relevant information. The population refers to the whole

group of people, events, or interesting things that the researcher wants to investigate (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). On the other hand, to select the customers in PosLaju outlet in Shah Alam who are the respondents in this research, a simple random sampling technique will be a good option. One of the probability samplings that is randomly selected from a larger sample or population is simple random sampling. Simple random sampling is a method used to cull a smaller sample size from a larger population and use it to research and make generalizations about the larger group. It is one of several methods statisticians and researchers use to extract a sample from a larger population; other methods include stratified random sampling and probability sampling. The advantages of a simple random sample include its ease of use and its accurate representation of the larger population (Podcast Research, 2017).

3.2.6.2 Sampling Frame and Sampling Location

According to Sekaran and Bougie (2016), the sampling frame is a representation (physical) of all the elements in the population from which the sample was taken. In this research, the sampling frame will be the customers that are already used PosLaju courier service. In fact, the sampling location for the survey will be in the PosLaju outlet in Shah Alam. PosLaju outlets in Shah Alam that have been chosen for this study are located as below.

Table 3: List of Selected PosLaju Outlet

PosLaju Outlet	Address
PosLaju Shah Alam	Jalan Paku 16/6, Seksyen 16, 40200 Shah Alam, Selangor
Pejabat Pos Besar	Persiaran Dato Menteri, Seksyen 12, 40670 Shah Alam, Selangor
Pos Malaysia Tesco Shah Alam	Lot No.7 Tesco Shah Alam, 3, Jalan Aerobik 13/43, Seksyen 13, 40100 Shah Alam, Selangor
Pos Malaysia @ Pejabat Pos UiTM Shah Alam	Jalan Ilmu 1/1, Universiti Institut Teknologi Mara, 40450, Shah Alam, Selangor

3.2.6.3 Sampling Elements

Respondents in this study referred to customers who perceived the courier service of PosLaju. A total of 384 respondents were selected for this study. The reason for choosing these sampling elements is because they are the main topic in this research since it is about the customer's service satisfaction and how it leads to customer loyalty.

3.2.6.4 Research Instrument

In this study, the researcher will construct a questionnaire that consists of four sections. In Section A, respondent's demographic profiles and three questions regarding their previous experience in courier service were asked. Section B dealt with the independent variables, which are tangibility, reliability, assurance, empathy, and responsiveness. Meanwhile, respondents will be asking about their satisfaction with the courier service in Section C and loyalty to use the same courier service in Section D. All questions in Section B, Section C, and Section D will be answered in 7-point Likert Scale as provided.

Table 4: Measurement Item for Section B, C and D

Construct	Original Item	Adapted Item	Source
Customer Satisfaction	1) I am satisfied with the safety and condition of my parcel. 2) I am satisfied with the postman of National Courier Services attitude.	1) I am satisfied with the safety and condition of my parcel. 2) I am satisfied with the postman of PosLaju attitude.	Adopted from Siali et al., (2018)

<p>Customer Loyalty</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) I would like to continue to shop at SUNING. 2) I would like to choose SUNING even if there are some other similar stores. 3) I would like to choose SUNING even if its commodity price raised. 4) I would like to recommend SUNING to other people. 5) I think I am a loyal customer of SUNING 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) I would like to continue to use PosLaju courier service. 2) I would like to choose PosLaju courier service even if there are some other similar service. 3) I would like to choose PosLaju courier service even if the price raised. 4) I would like to recommend PosLaju courier service to other people. 5) I think I am a loyal customer of PosLaju. 	<p>Adopted from Pei (2013)</p>
<p>Tangibility</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The hospital has modern looking equipment. 2) The physical facilities in the 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) PosLaju outlet has modern looking equipment. 	<p>Adopted from Komal Pancholi & P.K. Singh (2018)</p>

	<p>Hospital are visually appealing.</p> <p>3) Personnel in the hospital are neat in appearance.</p> <p>4) Materials associated with the service (such as pamphlets or statement) are visually appealing.</p>	<p>2) PosLaju physical facilities are visually appealing.</p> <p>3) PosLaju staff appears neat.</p> <p>4) Materials associated with the service are visually appealing.</p> <p>6) PosLaju outlet has convenient business hours.</p>	
Reliability	<p>1) National Courier Services postman are dependable.</p> <p>2) If National Courier Services promises to do something by a certain time, they do so.</p> <p>3) National Courier Services postman</p>	<p>1) PosLaju postman are dependable.</p> <p>2) If PosLaju promises to do something by a certain time, they do so.</p> <p>3) PosLaju postman delivers my parcel on time.</p> <p>4) PosLaju ensure that my parcel tracking</p>	Adopted from Siali et al., (2018)

	<p>delivers my parcel on time.</p> <p>4) National Courier Services make sure my parcel delivery tracking status is updated.</p> <p>5) National Courier Services inform or call me when they reach my house to deliver the parcels.</p>	<p>status is updated.</p> <p>5) PosLaju inform or call me when they reach my house to deliver the parcels.</p>	
Assurance	<p>1) When customers have problems, National Courier Services is kind and supportive.</p> <p>2) Customers feel safe in delivers their parcel with National Postage (National Courier Services).</p> <p>3) The postman of National</p>	<p>1) When customers have problems, the postman of PosLaju is kind and supportive.</p> <p>2) Customers feel safe in delivers their parcel using PosLaju.</p> <p>3) The postman of PosLaju assures customers.</p>	Adopted from Siali et al., (2018)

	<p>Courier Services assures customers.</p> <p>4) Postman of National Courier Services is polite.</p> <p>5) Postman of National Courier Services has the willingness to install confidence in customers.</p>	<p>4) Postman of PosLaju is polite.</p> <p>5) Postman of PosLaju has the willingness to install confidence in customers.</p>	
Empathy	<p>1) Customer service of National Courier Services is caring in serving their customers.</p> <p>2) National Courier Services give individual attention to customers.</p> <p>3) Postman of National Courier</p>	<p>1) Customer service of PosLaju is caring in serving their customers.</p> <p>2) PosLaju give individual attention to customers.</p> <p>3) Postman of PosLaju is aware of the customer's needs.</p> <p>4) The postman of PosLaju are</p>	Adopted from Siali et al., (2018)

	<p>Services is aware of the customer's needs.</p> <p>4) The postman of National Courier Services is easy to communicate with.</p> <p>5) Customer service of National Courier Services are always available for customers.</p>	<p>easy to communicate with.</p> <p>5) Customer service of PosLaju are always available for customers.</p>	
Responsiveness	<p>1) National Courier Services provide prompt service to customers.</p> <p>2) Postman of National Courier Services ready to help customers.</p> <p>3) Postman able to reply to any query or</p>	<p>1) PosLaju provide prompt service to customers.</p> <p>2) PosLaju ready to help customers.</p> <p>3) PosLaju able to reply to any query or question from customers.</p> <p>4) PosLaju care about their customers.</p>	<p>Adopted from Siali et al., (2018)</p>

	question from customers.		
	4) National Courier Services care about their customers.		5) PosLaju always delivers the right and actual parcel to customers.
	5) Postman of National Courier Services always delivers the right and actual parcel to customers.		

3.2.6.5 Sampling Size

Sampling is the process of using a small number of items or part of a larger population to determine the overall population (Mohiuddin et al., 2018). Sampling design is the ultimate way for researchers to collect accurate information for research questions from the right people, the right time, and location. Convenience sampling is the sampling that will be used in this research. Convenience sampling is defined as a method adopted by researchers where they collect market research data from a conveniently available pool of respondents. It is the most commonly used sampling technique as it's incredibly prompt, uncomplicated, and economical. In many cases, members are readily approachable to be a part of the sample. For example, the researcher will use Krejcie and Morgan (1970) table to construct a sample size based on a population. The researcher will use 384 respondents from the total population of Shah Alam, which consists of 650,000 people. Calculation of sample size is controlled by a 5% margin of error, 95% confidence level, and 50% response distribution.

Table 5: Demographic of Shah Alam

Source: (Majlis Bandaraya Shah Alam, 2014)

Shah Alam Area	290.3 sq. km
District	Petaling District and Part of Klang
Population	650,000 people
Number of Property Owners	212,938 unit (2014)
Sections	56 Sections
No. of Rivers	9
No. of Village	30
No. of Industries	18,880 units
No. of Shop / Office	10,116 units
Branch Office	3 branches
Recreation Area / Green	2,123.55 hectar

3.3 Pilot Study

Pilot study is defined as a small study which is to test the protocols of the research, data collection instruments, sample recruitment strategies and other type of research techniques in order to for the researcher to prepare for a larger study. Pilot study is considered as an important stage in a research project (Arain et al., 2010). That said, a group of 30 respondents will be selected to perform the pilot testing with a mini-scale questionnaire to ensure the proposed instrument is feasible and to assist in recognizing practical problems (if there is any) in following the research procedure.

3.4 Data Analysis

There are a few methods that are being used to analyze the data collected, and they are the descriptive statistic method, reliability test and validity, Pearson Correlation, and multivariate linear regression analysis. The result is generated and discussed after analyzing the date. The collected data will be keyed in using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences 24 (SPSS). Before data is analyzed, it will need to be cleaned for outliers and missing data. Outliers are points of data that are far or abnormally moved from the mass of data. It is important to address outliers before proceeding with statistical analysis.

Additionally, missing data is also capable of contaminating the results. Sometimes, participants intentionally or unintentionally choose not to respond to specific questions. Where the answers required to affect the analysis, the case will then need to be deleted and all information excluded from the analysis.

3.4.1 Descriptive Statistics

The brief description of a set of data that is either a representation of the entire population or a sample is called descriptive statistics. The main purpose is to provide a summary of the samples and measures done on a study. Descriptive statistics form a major component of all quantitative data analysis when coupled with several graphics' analyses. A descriptive statistic is more about describing what data is being shown and the behavior of a sample data. It is used to present a quantitative analysis of the given set of data. As in a study, there are numerous variables that are to be measured, and hence descriptive statistics is used to break this huge amount of data into the simplest form. The data collected in this research will be displayed graphically using bar, pie, and graph charts. After displaying the data graphically, an overall overview of the data can be obtained.

3.4.2 Demographic Information

The socio-demographic information that will be collected in Shah Alam will be discussed. The generated descriptive statistics will make it easier to report the demographic information in percentage.

3.4.3 Reliability and Validity

Reliability refers to how consistent the particular method is able to measure a variable. Consistently achieving the same results using the same method as measurement indicates good reliability. Statistically, an item or measure is reliable when Cronbach's alpha is $\alpha < .70$ (Taber, 2018). Extensively, validity is how well a method measures what it is purported to measure. High validity means the method or item accurately measures what needs to be measured (Heale & Twycross, 2017).

3.4.4 Multivariate Linear Regression Analysis

Multivariate linear regression is used when there is a need to measure the correlation between multiple independent variables and a single dependent variable. The R squared value depicts the percentage of the variance of the data, with the beta value indicating which variable has a higher impact on the dependent variable. Multiple regression analysis is used to identify the significant predictors of the dependent variable. The analysis will be done using SPSS.

3.5 Summary

Chapter three outlines the research method used in this study. The variables have been operationally defined and will be measured using questionnaires via Google form to limit person-to-person contact to comply with government restrictions. The collected data will be cleaned for outliers and missing values prior to analysis, as well as tested to meet the assumptions for multivariate analysis. The data will then be analyzed using SPSS. The data collected will then be discussed, and the results are displayed.

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS AND DATA ANALYSIS

4.1 Introduction

This chapter represents the analysis results as well as the data of SPSS. The SPSS analysis has been conducted based on the questionnaires distributed to 396 respondents. The data obtained was only from 376 respondents as 20 of them have not used PosLaju courier service in the last 6 months. The analysis and data were calculated using the SPSS Version 25 program. In this chapter, the discussion will start from the information of the respondents which is the demographics information. After that, the discussion will be followed by the reliability test, correlation analysis of variables as well as the results of the multivariate linear regression analysis.

4.2 Pilot Study

Table 6: Pilot Test

Variables	No. Of Items	Cronbach Alpha
Tangibility	5	0.957
Reliability	5	0.959
Assurance	5	0.981
Empathy	5	0.985
Responsiveness	5	0.978
Customer Satisfaction	6	0.977
Customer Loyalty	5	0.966

Reliability test is conducted in this research in order to determine if the results are consistent as well as if the variables are reliable or not reliable. In this reliability test, Cronbach Alpha will be used and the value based on Cronbach Alpha will determine and represent the correlation and standardization of all the elements in the questionnaires that have been distributed to the respondents. Reliability test helps to show and reflect if the data collected are reliable or not reliable. The table above, the

Cronbach Alpha's value is 0.992. This value is based on the overall 30 respondents under pilot study. The value indicates that all of the items are reliable. When the data is reliable, it shows the research is approved hence the distribution of questionnaires can be distributed to the respondents. Results summarised that tangibility (0.957), reliability (0.959), assurance (0.981), empathy (0.985), responsiveness (0.978), customers satisfaction (0.977) and customer loyalty (0.966) have Cronbach Alpha of above 0.9. This means that internal consistency is excellent which are based on the overall of 30 respondents under pilot study. Thus, the value indicates that all of the items are reliable. When the data is reliable, it shows that the research is approved hence the distribution of questionnaires can be distributed to the respondents.

4.3 Descriptive Analysis

4.3.1 Demographic Information

In this section, the analysis will discuss about the information of the respondents which is the demographics information. The demographic information includes gender, age, highest education level, employment status, frequency of using PosLaju courier service, and respondents' use of other courier services brands. Below is the table of respondents' demographic information.

Table 7: Respondent Gender

		Gender			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	197	52.4	52.4	52.4
	Female	179	47.6	47.6	100.0
	Total	376	100.0	100.0	

The above Table 8 shows the frequency distribution of all 376 respondents are under study. The data shows that 197 respondents (52.4%) are male whereas 179 respondents (47.6%) are female.

Table 8: Respondent Age

		Age Group			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	18 years old or below	29	7.7	7.7	7.7
	19 - 25 years old	63	16.8	16.8	24.5
	26 - 35 years old	144	38.3	38.3	62.8
	36 - 45 years old	100	26.6	26.6	89.4
	46 years old and above	40	10.6	10.6	100.0
	Total	376	100.0	100.0	

The table above shows the age of all the respondents. The data shows that most of the respondents are between the age of 26 to 35 years old with 144 respondents (38.3%). A total of 100 respondents (26.6%) are 36 to 45 years old, 63 respondents (16.8%) are 19 to 25 years old, 40 respondents (10.6%) are 46 years old and above and the last is 29 respondents (7.7%) are 18 years old and below.

Table 9: Respondents' Highest Education Level

		Highest Education Level			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	SPM	45	12.0	12.0	12.0
	STPM/Diploma	61	16.2	16.2	28.2
	Bachelor's Degree	157	41.8	41.8	69.9
	Master	93	24.7	24.7	94.7
	PhD	20	5.3	5.3	100.0
	Total	376	100.0	100.0	

From the table above, 45 respondents (12%) only has an education level of SPM, 61 respondents (16.2%) have STPM or diploma, 157 respondents (41.8%) has a bachelor's

degree, 93 respondents (24.7%) and the least number of respondents have PhD with only 20 respondents (5.3%).

Table 10: Respondents' Employment Status

		Employment Status			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Student	48	12.8	12.8	12.8
	Government Sector	43	11.4	11.4	24.2
	Private Sector	203	54.0	54.0	78.2
	Retired	7	1.9	1.9	80.1
	Self-employed	73	19.4	19.4	99.5
	Others	2	.5	.5	100.0
	Total	376	100.0	100.0	

Table 10 above illustrates the respondents' employment status. The respondents working in the private sector are dominant with 203 respondents (54%). This followed by respondents who are self-employed with 73 (19.4%), students with 48 (12.8%), government sector with 43 (11.4%), retirees with 7 (1.9%) and lastly other category with only 2 (0.5%).

Table 11: Respondents' Frequency of Using PosLaju Courier Service

Frequency of Using PosLaju Courier Service

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Once a month	159	42.3	42.3	42.3
	Twice a month	123	32.7	32.7	75.0
	One in 3 - 6 months	9	2.4	2.4	77.4
	Depends / When Necessary / When Needed	34	9.0	9.0	86.4
	Seldom	22	5.9	5.9	92.3
	Sometimes	4	1.1	1.1	93.4
	Frequent	20	5.3	5.3	98.7
	Always / All the time	5	1.3	1.3	100.0
	Total	376	100.0	100.0	

Table 11 shows that 159 respondents (42,3%) uses the PosLaju courier services once a month, followed by twice a month with 123 respondents (32.7%), 34 respondents (9%) only use the service when needed, 22 respondents (5.9%) seldom use the service and 20 respondents (5.3%) are frequent users. The remaining 4 (1.1%) and 5 (1.3%) are sometimes and all the time users of PosLaju courier services.

Table 12: Respondents' Use of Other Courier Services Brands

Use of other courier services brands

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	182	48.4	48.4	48.4
	No	194	51.6	51.6	100.0
	Total	376	100.0	100.0	

The table above shows that the data collected on the respondents' use of other courier services brands. A total of 182 respondents (48.4%) answered that they use other courier

services brands, whereas 194 respondents (51.6%) do not use other courier service brands.

4.3.2 Tangibility

Figure 5: Respondents' Response on PosLaju Having Modern Looking Equipment

The figure above shows that majority of the respondents with 306 (81%) of them agreeing that PosLaju do have a modern looking equipment. A total of 27 respondent (7%) disagreeing with the statement and 43 respondents (11%) have a neutral answer. The mean score of this variable is 5.57 with standard deviation of 1.265.

Figure 6: Respondents' Response on PosLaju Physical Facilities are Visually Appealing

The pie chart above illustrates that 313 respondents (83%) agreed that PosLaju physical facilities are visually appealing whereas 23 respondents (6%) of them do not agree with the statement. 40 respondents (11%) of them neither agree nor disagree with the statement. The mean for this variable is 5.61 and has a standard deviation of 1.217.

Figure 7: Respondents' Response on PosLaju Staff Uniform Appears Neat

The pie chart above shows that 326 respondents (87%) agrees that the uniform that PosLaju' staffs wear appears neat to them. On the contrary, 19 respondents (5%) of disagree whereas 67 respondents (18%) have a neutral answer. The mean and standard deviation for this variable is 5.74 and 1.115 respectively.

Figure 8: Respondents' Response on Materials Associated with the Service are Visually Appealing

From the figure above, the data shows that majority of the respondents with 320 (85%) of them feels that the material associated with the service are visually appealing in PosLaju whereas a mere 21 respondents (6%) of them disagree with it. A number of 35 respondents (9%) of them neither agree nor disagree with the statement above. This question has a mean of 5.68 with a standard deviation of 1.157.

Figure 9: Respondents' Response on PosLaju Outlets Have Convenient Business Hour

From the pie chart above, 327 respondents (87%) of the respondents find that PosLaju outlets have a convenient business hour whereas 18 respondents (5%) do not agree with the statement. The balance of 31 respondents (8%) neither agree nor disagree. The mean and standard deviation for this variable is 5.70 and 1.136.

4.3.3 Reliability

Figure 10: Respondents' Response on PosLaju Postmen are Dependable

The figure above shows that 321 respondents (85%) agree that PosLaju postmen are dependable. There are 18 respondents (5%) who do not agree that PosLaju postmen are dependable, and 37 respondents (10%) have a neutral answer. The mean for this variable is 5.71 with a standard deviation of 1.152.

Figure 11: Respondents' Response if PosLaju Promises to do Something by A Certain Time, They Do So

The pie chart above depicts the data on response from respondents on whether if PosLaju promises to do something by a certain time, they will do so. Majority of the respondents agrees with the statement with 307 respondents (82%), 23 respondents (6%) disagree whereas 46 respondents (12%) neither agree nor disagree with the statement. The mean and standard deviation on the other hand is 5.63 and 1.25.

Figure 12: Respondents' Response on PosLaju Postmen Deliver My Parcel on Time

The figure above illustrated the respondents' answered on whether PosLaju postmen deliver their parcel on time. The data collected shows that more than half of them agree that their parcel is delivered on time with 317 (84%). 25 respondents (7%) on the other hand does not agree to the statement, whereas 34 respondents (9%) neither agree nor disagree. The mean for this question is 5.67 with a standard deviation of 1.258.

Figure 13: Respondents' Response on PosLaju Ensures My Parcel Tracking Status Updated

The figure above shows that majority of the respondents 327 (87%) agree that PosLaju ensures their parcel tracking status is updated. The balance of 19 respondents (5%) and 30 respondents (8%) disagree and neither agree nor disagree to the statement above. The mean is 5.74 with a standard deviation of 1.194.

Figure 14: Respondents' Response on PosLaju Informs by Calling Me when They Reaching My House to Deliver the Parcels

From the above pie chart, the data shows that a huge portion of the respondents agree that PosLaju informs them by calling when they reach their house to deliver the parcel with 317 respondents (84%). Only 23 respondents (6%) do not agree that PosLaju calls them, and 36 respondents (10%) have a neutral answer. The overall mean for this question is 5.66 with a standard deviation of 1.250.

4.3.4 Assurance

Figure 15: Respondents' Response When Customers Have Problems, PosLaju Will Solve the Problems with Kindness

The pie chart in Figure 15, shows that most of the respondents with 319 (85%) agrees that PosLaju does solve their problems with kindness when they have any problems. On the contrary, 20 respondents (5%) do not agree with the statement, whereas 37 respondents (10%) neither agree nor disagree with the statement. The mean score for this is 5.64 with a standard deviation of 1.242.

Figure 16: Respondents' Response on Customers Feel that Their Parcel are in Good Hands with PosLaju

From Figure 16 above, the pie chart shows that 330 respondents (88%) agrees that their parcel are in good hands of PosLaju. Only 16 respondents (4%) disagree and 30 respondents (8%) neither agree nor disagree. The mean score is 5.74 with a standard deviation of 1.139.

Figure 17: Respondents' Response if PosLaju Assures Customers of Their Parcels' Safety

The figure above shows the data collected on whether PosLaju assures their customers of their parcels' safety. A number 323 respondents amounting to 86% agree with the statement, whereas 15 respondents (4%) disagree. The balance of 38 respondents or 10% neither agree nor disagree. The mean and standard deviation are 5.73 and 1.155.

Figure 18: Respondents' Response on PosLaju Promises on Time Service Delivery

The pie chart above shows that response on whether PosLaju promises on time service delivery. The data collected shows that 321 respondents (83%) agrees that PosLaju do deliver their parcel on time. There is 20 respondents (5%) who do not agree with PosLaju on time service delivery promises, whereas 35 respondents (9%) have a neutral answer. The mean for this question is 5.68 with a standard deviation of 1.202.

Figure 19: Respondents' Response on PosLaju Assures Confidence in Serving Customers

From the pie above figure, the data collected shows that 322 respondents (86%) agree that PosLaju do assure confidence in serving customers. There are 21 respondents (5%) who do not agree with the statement and 33 respondents (9%) have a neutral answer. The mean score is 5.72 with standard deviation of 1.205.

Figure 20: Respondents' Response on PosLaju is Caring in Serving their Customer

The pie chart in Figure 20 shows that vast majority of the respondents agree that PosLaju is caring in serving their customers. This supported with 324 respondents (86%) agreeing to the statement. There are only 18 respondents (5%) who disagree, while 34 respondents (9%) neither agree nor disagree. The mean score for this is 5.69 with a standard deviation of 1.201.

Figure 21: Respondents' Response on PosLaju Gives Individual Attention to Customer

The pie chart above shows that 321 respondents (85%) agree that PosLaju do give individual attention to their customer. There is only a very little number who disagree with 21 respondents (6%), whereas 34 respondents (9%) neither agree nor disagree with the statement. The mean score is 5.65 with a standard deviation of 1.235.

4.3.5 Empathy

Figure 22: Respondents' Response on PosLaju Being Aware of the Customers' Needs

Figure 22 shows that most of the respondents agrees that PosLaju is aware of the customers' needs with 322 (86%) of them. On the other hand, only 20 (5%) of them disagree and 34 (9%) of them neither agree nor disagree. The mean score is 5.68 with a standard deviation of 1.216.

Figure 23: Respondents' Response on PosLaju Employees are Easy to Communicate With

From the figure above, it shows that majority of 330 respondents (88%) agree that PosLaju employees are easy to communicate with. Only 18 respondents (5%) disagree, whereas there are 28 respondents (7%) neither agree nor disagree. The mean score is 5.71 with a standard deviation of 1.197.

Figure 24: Respondents' Response on Customer Service of PosLaju is Always Available for Customers

The pie chart above shows that the customer service of PosLaju is always available for customers with 322 respondents (86%) agreeing to it. Another 20 (5%) of the respondents do not agree and 34 (9%) neither agree nor disagree. The mean score is 5.69 with a standard deviation of 1.248.

4.3.6 Responsiveness

Figure 25: Respondents' Response on PosLaju Provides Prompt Services to Customers

The above figures illustrate the fact that, most of the respondents agree that PosLaju do provide prompt services to customers with a staggering 321 or 85%. There are only 24 respondents or 6% of them who disagree and the balance of 31 respondents or 8% neither agree nor disagree. The mean score is 5.68 and the standard deviation is 1.216.

Figure 26: Respondents' Response on PosLaju is Ever Ready to Help Customers

From the figure above, most of the respondents agree that PosLaju is ever ready to help customers with 321 or 85%. There are only 24 respondents or 6% of them who disagree and the balance of 31 respondents or 9% neither agree nor disagree. The mean score is 5.71 and the standard deviation is 1.182.

Figure 27: Respondents' Response on PosLaju Always Reply to Customers' Query/Question

The pie chart above shows if PosLaju is ready to help their customers. Majority with 323 respondents (86%) agree with the statement, whereas only 21 respondents (6%) disagree. There are 32 respondents (9%) neither agree nor disagree. The mean score is 5.72 and the standard deviation is 1.202.

Figure 28: Respondents' Response on PosLaju Cares About Their Customer

The pie chart above shows that most of the respondents agree that PosLaju cares about their customers with 325 respondents (86%). There are only 20 respondents (5%) who do not feel that PosLaju cares about them, while 34 respondents (9%) have a neutral answer. The mean score is 5.69 and the standard deviation is 1.221.

Figure 29: Respondents' Response on PosLaju Always Delivers the Right Parcels to Customer with No Mixed-up

The figure above shows the response from respondents on PosLaju delivering the right parcel to customers without mixing up. The respondents mostly agree to the statement with 329 (88%). Only 12 respondents (3%) disagree and the balance of 35 (9%) respondents neither agree nor disagree. The mean score is 5.78 and the standard deviation is 1.113.

4.3.7 Customer Satisfaction

Figure 30: Respondents' Response on I am Satisfied with the Safety of My Parcel

The above chart shows that 343 respondents (91%) answered of being satisfied with the safety of their parcel, whereas 15 respondents (4%) are dissatisfied. A balance 18 respondents (5%) have a neutral answer. The mean for this question is 5.89 with a standard deviation of 1.085.

Figure 31: Respondents' Response on I am Satisfied with the Condition of My Parcel

The figure above shows that 344 respondents (91%) agree that they do feel satisfied with the condition of their parcel. There is only 13 respondent (4%) who are not satisfied and the balance of 19 respondents (5%) neither agree nor disagree. The mean for this question is 5.89 with a standard deviation of 1.038.

Figure 32: Respondents' Response on I am Happy with the Postmen's Attitude

From the figure above, it shown that more than half of the respondents with 314 (91%) agree that they are happy with the attitude of the postmen. Only 13 respondents (3%) disagree and the balance of 63 respondents (17%) neither agree nor disagree. The mean value is 5.86 with a standard deviation of 1.073.

Figure 33: Respondents' Response on the Courier Services of PosLaju Met My Expectation

The pie chart above illustrates if whether the courier services that is provided by PosLaju met the respondents' expectations. From the data collected, it can be seen that a huge portion of the respondents find that PosLaju does met their expectations with 340 respondents or 90%. There are only a mere 16 respondents or 5% who do not agree and the balance 20 respondents or 5% have a neutral answer. The mean for this question is 5.86 with standard deviation of 1.106.

Figure 34: Respondents' Response on Being Satisfied with Customer Services Provided by PosLaju

The above figures illustrate the fact that majority of the respondents with 337 or 90% of them find that they are satisfied with the customer services provided by PosLaju. There are only 20 respondents or 5% who are not satisfied and the balance 19 respondents or 5% have a neutral answer. The mean is 5.85 with a standard deviation of 1.151.

Figure 35: Respondents' Response on Overall being Satisfied with PosLaju Services

The chart shows that 338 respondents (90%) are overall satisfied with PosLaju services. There are only 17 respondents (5%) disagree of being satisfied with the overall PosLaju services and 21 respondents (6%) neither agree nor disagree. The mean score is 5.86 with 1.110 standard deviation.

4.3.8 Customer Loyalty

Figure 36: Response on Whether Respondents' Would Continue Using PosLaju Courier Service in the Future

From the figure above, it can be seen that most of the respondents will continue using PosLaju courier service in the future with 331 respondents (88%). There are only 14 respondents who will not continue using PosLaju and the balance 31 respondent neither agree nor disagree. The mean score is 5.85 with a 1.125 standard deviation.

Figure 37: Respondents' Response on I Would Still Choose PosLaju Courier Service Even When There are Other Similar Services Available

The data shows that 317 respondents or 84% will choose PosLaju courier service even when there are other similar services available. Other respondents with only 26 (7%) of them disagree and would choose other courier services. The balance of 33 (9%) respondents neither agree nor disagree. The score of mean for this question is 5.73 and the standard deviation is 1.29.

Figure 38: Respondents' Response on I Would Choose PosLaju Courier Service Even if They Increase the Price

The pie chart shows that 288 (77%) respondents would still choose PosLaju courier service even if they increase the price. There are only 37 respondents (9%) will not choose PosLaju, whereas the balance of 51 respondents (14%) has a neutral answer. The mean is 5.40 with standard deviation of 1.47.

Figure 39: Respondents' Response on I Would Recommend PosLaju Courier Services to Other People

Figure 39 shows that 318 respondents (85%) will recommend using PosLaju courier services to other people. Only 23 respondents (6%) states that they would not recommend. The balance of 35 respondents (9%) has a neutral answer. The mean is 5.73 with 1.327 standard deviation.

Figure 40: Response on Respondents Being a Loyal Customer of PosLaju

The pie chart above illustrates that majority of the respondents think that they are a loyal customer of PosLaju with 309 or 82%. There are only 33 (9%) respondents who does not think themselves as loyal PosLaju customers and the balance 34 (9%) respondents are neutral. The mean is 5.65 with standard deviation of 1.417.

4.4 Reliability Analysis

Table 13: Reliability Test

Variables	No. Of Items	Cronbach Alpha Pilot Test (N=30)	Cronbach Alpha Actual Study (N=376)
Tangibility	5	0.957	0.967
Reliability	5	0.959	0.970
Assurance	5	0.981	0.986
Empathy	5	0.985	0.988
Responsiveness	5	0.978	0.952
Customer Satisfaction	6	0.977	0.984
Customer Loyalty	5	0.966	0.976

The above table summarised the Cronbach Alpha scores for the study's variables ranging from lowest 0.952 (Responsiveness) to highest 0.988 (Empathy). Comparison between the scores from the pilot test, it was found that the Cronbach Alpha for all variables have increased except for Responsiveness score which slightly decrease has from 0.978 to 0.952 from the pilot test score. However, as the Cronbach Alpha values were above 0.9, which conclude both pilot study for the 30 respondents and the reliability analysis for 376 respondents showed good internal consistency that contributed to the high validity and reliability of the instruments.

4.5 Correlation Analysis

A Pearson Correlation is used to evaluate the relationship between two variables. Between the two variables, the intensity of the two variables is tested. The positive correlation and the negative correlation are the two types of Pearson correlations. A change in one variable's magnitude will affect the other variable in either a positive or negative correlation direction. The range and the strength of the variables are described in the table below.

Table 14: Coefficient Range and Strength (Taber, 2017)

Coefficient Range	Strength
+1 to -1	Perfect
+0.9 to -0.9	Strong
+0.8 to -0.8	Strong
+0.7 to -0.7	Strong
+0.6 to -0.6	Moderate
+0.5 to -0.5	Moderate
+0.4 to -0.4	Moderate
+0.3 to -0.3	Weak
+0.2 to -0.2	Weak
+0.1 to -0.1	Weak
0	Zero

The table below shows the Pearson Correlation's value of all the 7 variable which is being used in this study.

Table 15: Pearson Correlation of Seven Variables (N=376)

		Tangibility	Reliability	Assurance	Empathy	Responsiveness	Customer Satisfaction	Customer Loyalty
Tangibility	Pearson Correlation	1	.849**	.861**	.848**	.858**	.806**	.766**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
Reliability	Pearson Correlation	.849**	1	.921**	.891**	.889**	.861**	.776**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
Assurance	Pearson Correlation	.861**	.921**	1	.935**	.929**	.890**	.818**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000	.000	.000
Empathy	Pearson Correlation	.848**	.891**	.935**	1	.952**	.896**	.840**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000	.000	.000
Responsiveness	Pearson Correlation	.858**	.889**	.929**	.952**	1	.920**	.846**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000		.000	.000
Customer Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	.806**	.861**	.890**	.896**	.920**	1	.847**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000		.000
Customer Loyalty	Pearson Correlation	.766**	.776**	.818**	.840**	.846**	.847**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Results illustrated in Table 15 shows Pearson Correlation of seven variables. A correlation between variables indicates that as one variable changes in value, the other

variable tends to change in a specific direction. The relationship between the variables is useful as the value of one variable can be used to predict the value of the other variable. This correlation coefficient is a single number that measures both the strength and direction of the linear relationship between two continuous variables. Values can range from -1 to +1. The greater the absolute value of the correlation coefficient, the stronger the relationship. The extreme values of -1 and 1 indicate a perfectly linear relationship where a change in one variable is accompanied by a perfectly consistent change in the other. For these relationships, all the data points fall on a line. A coefficient of zero represents no linear relationship. As one variable increases, there is no tendency in the other variable to either increase or decrease.

From the above table, it shows the Pearson Correlation between tangibility and customers satisfaction value at 0.806. This implies that the correlation between these two variables are strong and have a positive correlation. Moreover, the significant value is 0.00 which indicates that the correlation is significant. This suggests that if the tangibility increases, it will cause the customer's satisfaction to also increase. The table also shows a positive and strong correlation between tangibility and customer's loyalty. Hence, if tangibility increases, there will be an increase in the customer's loyalty.

Besides that, the table shows the correlation between reliability and customers satisfaction. There is a positive correlation between the two variables with a coefficient of 0.861. It indicates that when the reliability of PosLaju increases, it will have an increase in the customers' satisfaction in using PosLaju. Furthermore, reliability also has a correlation of 0.776 with customer loyalty which is a positive coefficient. Thus, the increase in reliability also directly increases customers loyalty.

Furthermore, there is a positive relationship between assurance and customers satisfaction with a value of 0.890 and a significant value of 0.000, which indicates the correlation is significant. Therefore, an increase in assurance by PosLaju will increase the satisfaction of the customers. Assurance also has a solid and positive relationship between customer's loyalty with a coefficient of 0.818. It implies that if the assurance of PosLaju increases, it also increases the customer's loyalty using PosLaju.

Empathy has a strong and positive relationship between customers satisfaction. The coefficient of 0.896 indicated that if there is an increase in PosLaju's empathy, the customer satisfaction will also increase. However, empathy on the other hand also have

a Pearson Correlation of 0.840 with customer's loyalty. This implies that the correlation between the variable is positive and strong. An increase in empathy will directly increase customer's loyalty. Lastly, the Pearson Correlation between responsiveness and customer's satisfaction is 0.920 which indicates a strong and positive correlation. If the responsiveness of PosLaju increases, hence the customer's satisfaction will also increase. This can be seen the same in responsiveness and customers' loyalty where the correlation between the two variables is 0.846 which is strong and positive. Increase in responsiveness will also cause an increase in customers' loyalty.

4.6 Multivariate Linear Regression Analysis

Table 16: The Relationship Between Tangibility and Customer Satisfaction

Model Summary ^b										
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.806 ^a	.649	.649	.61401	.649	692.924	1	374	.000	1.774
a. Predictors: (Constant), Tangibility b. Dependent Variable: Customer Satisfaction										

In this study, the multivariate linear regression analysis is used as a statistical technique to analyse the linear relationship between dependent variable and independent variables. This is a way to recognize whether there is significant relationship between independent variables and dependent variables or not. The model sufficiently explained the variance or coefficient of determination or the R Squared in the effect of control variables relations. R Squared is the percentage of variation in the response that is explained by the model. The higher the R Square value, the better the model fits the data. R Squared is always between 0% and 100%. Based on available data as shown in above table, the R Square value is 0.65. This indicates that 65% of the total variance in

customer satisfaction is explained based on the independent variables which are tangibility.

Table 17: Anova of Regression Between Tangibility and Customer Satisfaction

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	261.234	1	261.234	692.924	.000 ^b
	Residual	140.999	374	.377		
	Total	402.233	375			
a. Dependent Variable: Customer Satisfaction						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Tangibility						

The ANOVA table above shows a significant value of 0.00, which indicates the model is fit and can be used for further analysis. The significant value must be 0.005 and below to prove that there is goodness-of-fit between the data and model. This proposes that the independent variables can affect the dependent variable. The value 0.00 is less than 0.05 (typically ≤ 0.05) is statistically significant. It indicates strong evidence against the null hypothesis, as there is less than a 5% probability the null is correct. Therefore, the hypothesis that tangibility has a positive relation with customer satisfaction is accepted.

Table 18: The Relationship Between Tangibility and Customer Loyalty

Model Summary ^b										
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.766 ^a	.586	.585	.80480	.586	529.981	1	374	.000	1.580

a. Predictors: (Constant), Tangibility
b. Dependent Variable: Customer Loyalty

Based on available data as shown in above table, the R Square value is 0.57. This indicates that 57% of the total variance in customer loyalty is explained based on the independent variables which is tangibility.

Table 19: Anova of Regression Between Tangibility and Customer Loyalty

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	343.267	1	343.267	529.981	.000 ^b
	Residual	242.238	374	.648		
	Total	585.505	375			

a. Dependent Variable: Customer Loyalty
b. Predictors: (Constant), Tangibility

The ANOVA table above shows a significant P-value of 0.00, which indicates the model is fit and can be used for further analysis. The hypothesis that tangibility has a positive relationship with customers loyalty is thus accepted.

Table 20: The Relationship Between Reliability and Customer Satisfaction

Model Summary ^b										
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.861 ^a	.741	.741	.52754	.741	1071.338	1	374	.000	1.746

a. Predictors: (Constant), Reliability
b. Dependent Variable: Customer Satisfaction

Based on the data as shown in above table, the R square value is 0.74. This indicates that 74% of the total variance in customer satisfaction is explained based on the independent variables which is reliability.

Table 21: Anova of Regression Between Reliability and Customer Satisfaction

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	298.150	1	298.150	1071.338	.000 ^b
	Residual	104.083	374	.278		
	Total	402.233	375			

a. Dependent Variable: Customer Satisfaction
b. Predictors: (Constant), Reliability

The ANOVA table above shows a significant P-value of 0.00, which indicates the model is fit and can be used for further analysis. The hypothesis that reliability has a positive relationship with customers satisfaction is thus accepted.

Table 22: The Relationship Between Reliability and Customer Loyalty

Model Summary ^b										
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.776 ^a	.602	.601	.78895	.602	566.654	1	374	.000	1.538

a. Predictors: (Constant), Reliability
b. Dependent Variable: Customer Loyalty

The table above shows the R Squared value of 0.60 which means that 60% of the total variance in customer loyalty is explained based on the independent variables which is reliability.

Table 23: Anova of Regression Between Reliability and Customer Loyalty

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	352.711	1	352.711	566.654	.000 ^b
	Residual	232.794	374	.622		
	Total	585.505	375			

a. Dependent Variable: Customer Loyalty
b. Predictors: (Constant), Reliability

The ANOVA table above shows a significant P-value of 0.00, which indicates the model is fit and can be used for further analysis. The hypothesis that reliability has a positive relationship with customers loyalty is thus accepted.

Table 24: The Relationship Between Assurance and Customer Satisfaction

Model Summary ^b										
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.890 ^a	.793	.792	.47216	.793	1430.285	1	374	.000	1.846

a. Predictors: (Constant), Assurance
b. Dependent Variable: Customer Satisfaction

Based on available data as shown in above table, the R square value is 0.79. This indicates that 79% of the total variance in customer satisfaction is explained based on the independent variables which is assurance.

Table 25: Anova of Regression Between Assurance and Customer Satisfaction

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	318.857	1	318.857	1430.285	.000 ^b
	Residual	83.377	374	.223		
	Total	402.233	375			

a. Dependent Variable: Customer Satisfaction
b. Predictors: (Constant), Assurance

The ANOVA table above shows a significant P-value of 0.00, which indicates the model is fit and can be used for further analysis. The hypothesis that assurance has a positive relationship with customers satisfaction is thus accepted.

Table 26: The Relationship Between Assurance and Customer Loyalty

Model Summary ^b										
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.818 ^a	.669	.668	.71987	.669	755.869	1	374	.000	1.593

a. Predictors: (Constant), Assurance
b. Dependent Variable: Customer Loyalty

Based on available data as shown in above table, the R square value is 0.67. This indicates that 67% of the total variance in customer loyalty is explained based on the independent variables which is assurance.

Table 27: Anova of Regression Between Assurance and Customer Loyalty

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	391.696	1	391.696	755.869	.000 ^b
	Residual	193.809	374	.518		
	Total	585.505	375			

a. Dependent Variable: Customer Loyalty
b. Predictors: (Constant), Assurance

The ANOVA table above shows a significant P-value of 0.00, which indicates the model is fit and can be used for further analysis. The hypothesis that assurance has a positive relationship with customers loyalty is thus accepted.

Table 28: The Relationship Between Empathy and Customer Satisfaction

Model Summary ^b										
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.896 ^a	.803	.803	.46015	.803	1525.699	1	374	.000	1.852

a. Predictors: (Constant), Empathy
b. Dependent Variable: Customer Satisfaction

From the analysis above, the R square value is 0.80 which means that 80% of the total variance in customer satisfaction is explained based on the independent variables which is empathy.

Table 29: Anova of Regression Between Empathy and Customer Satisfaction

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	323.044	1	323.044	1525.699	.000 ^b
	Residual	79.189	374	.212		
	Total	402.233	375			

a. Dependent Variable: Customer Satisfaction
b. Predictors: (Constant), Empathy

The ANOVA table above shows a significant P-value of 0.00, which indicates the model is fit and can be used for further analysis. The hypothesis that empathy has a positive relationship with customers satisfaction is thus accepted.

Table 30: The Relationship Between Empathy and Customer Loyalty

Model Summary ^b										
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.840 ^a	.706	.705	.67893	.706	896.214	1	374	.000	1.560

a. Predictors: (Constant), Empathy
b. Dependent Variable: Customer Loyalty

Based on available data as shown in above table, the R square value is 0.71. This indicates that 71% of the total variance in customer loyalty is explained based on the independent variables which is empathy.

Table 31: Anova of Regression Between Empathy and Customer Loyalty

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	413.109	1	413.109	896.214	.000 ^b
	Residual	172.395	374	.461		
	Total	585.505	375			

a. Dependent Variable: Customer Loyalty
b. Predictors: (Constant), Empathy

The ANOVA table above shows a significant P-value of 0.00, which indicates the model is fit and can be used for further analysis. The hypothesis that empathy has a positive relationship with customers loyalty is thus accepted.

Table 32: The Relationship Between Responsiveness and Customer Satisfaction

Model Summary ^b										
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.920 ^a	.846	.846	.40697	.846	2054.586	1	374	.000	1.675
a. Predictors: (Constant), Responsiveness										
b. Dependent Variable: Customer Satisfaction										

The table above shows the R square value is 0.85. This indicates that 85% of the total variance in customer satisfaction is explained based on the independent variables which is responsiveness.

Table 33: Anova of Regression Between Responsiveness and Customer Satisfaction

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	340.290	1	340.290	2054.586	.000 ^b
	Residual	61.944	374	.166		
	Total	402.233	375			
a. Dependent Variable: Customer Satisfaction						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Responsiveness						

The ANOVA table above shows a significant P-value of 0.00, which indicates the model is fit and can be used for further analysis. The hypothesis that responsiveness has a positive relationship with customers satisfaction is thus accepted.

Table 34: The Relationship Between Responsiveness and Customer Loyalty

Model Summary ^b										
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.846 ^a	.716	.715	.66707	.716	941.783	1	374	.000	1.370
a. Predictors: (Constant), Responsiveness b. Dependent Variable: Customer Loyalty										

Based on available data as shown in above table, the R square value is 0.72. This indicates that 72% of the total variance in customer loyalty is explained based on the independent variables which is responsiveness.

Table 35: Anova of Regression Between Responsiveness and Customer Loyalty

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	419.080	1	419.080	941.783	.000 ^b
	Residual	166.425	374	.445		
	Total	585.505	375			
a. Dependent Variable: Customer Loyalty b. Predictors: (Constant), Responsiveness						

The ANOVA table above shows a significant P-value of 0.00, which indicates the model is fit and can be used for further analysis. The hypothesis that responsiveness has a positive relationship with customers loyalty is thus accepted.

4.7 Discussion

From the research findings, this study provides a perspective of respondents on customers satisfaction and customer loyalty on PosLaju courier service quality in Malaysia. This research successfully answered the research objectives. The answers below are based on the hypothesis given at the beginning of the research.

H1a: There is positive relationship between tangibility with customer satisfaction

H1b: There is positive relationship between tangibility with customer loyalty

Based on the survey data collected from 376 respondents, the data analysis shows that more than half of the respondents find that PosLaju have modern looking equipment and visually appealing facilities. Tangibles are associated with the physical facilities, tools, and machines used in order to provide the service, as well as representations of the services. It is the physical image of the service that customers will use to assess quality (Parasuraman, 1988). This tangibility has a positive impact on the customers satisfaction. If the physical equipment and facilities offered by PosLaju are up to date and appealing, it will make the customers to be more satisfied and thus leading to them using the courier service over again. This then creates customer loyalty among PosLaju courier service users. Pearson Correlation also shows a positive relationship between tangibility with customers satisfaction and tangibility with customer loyalty. Tangibility with customers satisfaction and customer loyalty have a strong correlation with 0.806 and 0.766. This correlation thus enables both hypotheses above to be accepted.

H2a: There is positive relationship between reliability with customer satisfaction

H2b: There is positive relationship between reliability with customer loyalty

This study also serves to examine the relationship between reliability with customers satisfaction and customers loyalty. From the data analysis conducted, most of the respondents find that PosLaju is reliable with respondents agreeing that PosLaju's postmen are dependable and they deliver their parcel on time. From the Pearson Correlation being conducted, it is also proved that reliability has a positive relationship

between customers satisfaction and also customers loyalty. Reliability means that Poslaju have perform a service correctly the first time and shows that they strive to fulfil promises and pay attention to the results. When the service provided by PosLaju are reliable, it thus provides satisfaction to the customers which then leads to customers loyalty. Pearson correlation also shows a positive correlation between reliability with customer satisfaction and loyalty with 0.861 and 0.776. Hence, the hypothesis for this is accepted.

H3a: There is positive relationship between assurance with customer satisfaction

H3b: There is positive relationship between assurance with customer loyalty

Assurance has been one of the main factor of customers satisfaction and customers loyalty. Data from the survey results collected shows that majority agreed that assurance such as assuring on time service delivery is very important is providing customers satisfaction. Assurance means keeping customers informed, listening to them, regardless of their educational level, age, and nationality. When PosLaju is able to deliver as such, they not only satisfy their customers but also ensure the loyalty to their courier services. The Pearson Correlation has managed to show a positive relationship between assurance and customers satisfaction and customers loyalty with 0.890 and 0.818. Hence, this hypothesis is also accepted.

H4a: There is positive relationship between empathy with customer satisfaction

H4b: There is positive relationship between empathy with customer loyalty

Furthermore, this study also managed to prove the hypothesis right of the positive relationship between empathy with customers satisfaction and customer loyalty. Customers need to feel that they are made priority by the courier service provider. Empathy means caring, paying personal attention, and providing services to customers. The core of empathy is conveying the feeling that the customer is unique and special. From the survey data collected, most of the respondents find that PosLaju is aware of the customers' needs and PosLaju customers service is always available for them. The data also showed that the respondents feel that PosLalu have met their expectations and are satisfied with their service. This then leads to customers loyalty with 88% of the

customer said they will continue using PosLaju courier service. Empathy has a positive correlation with customer satisfaction and customer loyalty with 0.896 and 8.40. Both the value has a strong positive relationship. This hypothesis is also accepted for this study.

H5a: There is positive relationship between responsiveness with customer satisfaction

H5b: There is positive relationship between responsiveness with customer loyalty

Lastly, this research also serves to study the positive relationship between responsiveness with customers satisfaction and customers loyalty. The Pearson Correlation data shows a positive relationship between responsiveness with customer satisfaction and loyalty with values 0.920 ad 0.845. Responsiveness is the willingness of PosLaju involving telling customers exactly when things will be done, giving them undivided attention, promoting services, and responding in accordance with their requests. Most of the respondents finds that PosLaju provides prompt service to their customers and as well as being ever ready to serve them. With this dimension, the customer will feel they are important to PosLaju. Besides, employees must be able to respond to any inquiries that has been given by their customer. And this will eventually lead to the customer loyalty to the service provider. This study thus is able to accept the hypotheses.

Table 36: Summary of Hypotheses

Hypotheses	p-value	Results
H1a: There is positive relationship between tangibility with customer satisfaction	0.000	Hypothesis Accepted
H1b: There is positive relationship between tangibility with customer loyalty	0.000	Hypothesis Accepted

H2a: There is positive relationship between reliability with customer satisfaction	0.000	Hypothesis Accepted
H2b: There is positive relationship between reliability with customer loyalty	0.000	Hypothesis Accepted
H3a: There is positive relationship between assurance with customer satisfaction	0.000	Hypothesis Accepted
H3b: There is positive relationship between assurance with customer loyalty	0.000	Hypothesis Accepted
H4a: There is positive relationship between empathy with customer satisfaction	0.000	Hypothesis Accepted
H4b: There is positive relationship between empathy with customer loyalty	0.000	Hypothesis Accepted
H5a: There is positive relationship between responsiveness with customer satisfaction	0.000	Hypothesis Accepted
H5b: There is positive relationship between responsiveness with customer loyalty	0.000	Hypothesis Accepted

4.8 Conclusion

This chapter reviewed all the results from analysis of data that were collected from the 376 respondents. Moreover, this chapter also provides the demographic information of the respondents includes gender, age, education level, employment status, and frequency of using PosLaju courier services. Furthermore, few tests such as reliability test, correlation and regression analysis were conducted and the results of those tests were explained in details in this chapter.

CHAPTER FIVE

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 Introduction

Courier services have always been a supporting function for production and consumption in previous decades. Functions are only considered a cost for typical courier service firms. However, since the 1990s, this view has begun to shift in the marketing concept used to evaluate courier service capacity, resulting in increased customer pleasure and loyalty (Mentzer et al., 2001). Since the arrival of the first international courier service provider, DHL, into Malaysia in the 1970s, the courier services sector in Malaysia has been facing increasing competition (Ho et al., 2012). Customer happiness and service quality are important aspects of business since a company's growth is largely dependent on how well it maintains its customers through service. Customer satisfaction is predicted to grow as a result of high service quality, which will boost customer retention and loyalty. Customer satisfaction is a result of good service quality, which makes businesses more competitive in the market. Identifying issues in service and setting measurements for service performances and results, as well as customer happiness, may lead to high service quality. Furthermore, the discrepancies between expected and perceived service may be used to determine service quality. Customer happiness and service quality have a favourable link.

In this chapter, a summary of the research will be outlined. Thus, in this chapter will also discuss on the limitation of the study. Furthermore, in order for future research to continue this research in depth, there will be recommendations included at the end of the chapter.

5.2 Overall Findings

The main objective why this study is being conducted is to find the customer satisfaction and customers loyalty on courier service quality in Malaysian for PosLaju. Based on the results obtain from the data analysis, the hypothesis generated for this study is accepted. Based on the descriptive analysis and Pearson's Correlation test, all

of the variables have a positive relationship between on one another. Specifically, this research was done to meet the following objectives.

- a) To analyze the relationship between **tangibility** with customer satisfaction and customer loyalty.
- b) To explore the relationship between **reliability** with customer satisfaction and customer loyalty.
- c) To examine the relationship between **assurance** with customer satisfaction and customer loyalty.
- d) To find out the relationship between **empathy** with customer satisfaction and customer loyalty.
- e) To determine the relationship between **responsiveness** with customer satisfaction and customer loyalty.
- f) To determine the relationship between **customer satisfaction** and **customer loyalty**?

Based on the literature review and data analysis done in Chapter 2 and Chapter 4, all of the above objectives have been achieved successfully in this paper. This paper has been able to find out how tangibility, reliability, assurance, empathy and responsiveness impacts customers satisfaction and their loyalty towards PosLaju usage. The results reveal that tangibility has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction. Most of the respondents were satisfied with the equipments and physical facilities that the PosLaju has provided them with. Additionally, the customers satisfaction is also positively impacted by the reliability offered by PosLaju. This is true because the respondents have agreed that Poslaju postmen are reliable, and they deliver their parcel on time. Assurance is a primary factor, together with reliability, access, and employee competences. The assurance dimension was found to have a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction. The customers of PosLaju have showed their satisfaction in terms of the assurance of knowledge, courtesy, and the ability to inspire confidence in customers. This can be seen when the data collected showed that

PosLaju assured that the products will be delivered on time and most respondents agree to it.

Moreover, empathy also proved to be significantly related to customer satisfaction. With a good communication and understanding of customer needs and friendly behavior, empathy will be achieved. The result implies that customers of PosLaju agree that PosLaju are aware of their needs and are available for them. This may instil confidence in the customers which enhances their confidence. Responsiveness also affects the customers satisfaction positively. The result shows that the respondents were satisfied with the responsiveness of the employees of PosLaju as they provide prompt services and are always ready to help. All the variable above positively impacts customers satisfaction. When the customers are satisfied, they will return to use the courier service again and hence PosLaju have gained customers who are loyal to them.

5.3 Summary

The main purpose of why this research is conducted is to find out the customer satisfaction and customers loyalty on PosLaju courier service quality in Malaysia. Throughout this study, it shows that customers satisfaction is very important on the service quality that is provided by PosLaju to its customers. This customers satisfaction will eventually lead to customers loyalty in using their courier services. The study shows that tangibility, reliability, assurance, empathy and responsiveness are the important contributors to customers satisfaction and loyalty. Courier services that focus on these five aspects will be able to retain their customers based on their satisfaction and loyalty.

5.4 Recommendations for Future Research

There are a few recommendations that future researcher can use in order to improve their research. The first recommendation will be to increase the number of respondents in the study. Research that has a large number of respondents can improve the reliability and validity of the research. The future researchers can have a larger

number of respondents that covers a diverse category of general citizens and also some public sectors respondents.

Secondly, this study focuses on the responses of respondents who only uses PosLaju courier services. The study does not include response of respondents who have not used the courier service for the last six months. This means that the chosen respondents answering the questionnaire based on their perceptions, which may result in bias results. They may favor PosLaju, and the study does not get results from those who chose not to continue using the courier service. This research does not provide any general citizens perspectives. The results can be improved by examining the findings using a broader and more representative sample set, such as the general population, to obtain more reliable results.

Thirdly, future research can do their study and gain other factors that may influence the customers satisfaction and customers loyalty. There are many other independent variables that can affect customers satisfaction and loyalty and it can be discussed in the new research. As a result, the new research findings will help to resolve and improve the customers satisfaction and customers loyalty towards PosLaju

Fourth, future researchers can utilize the same variables used in this study and conduct the research study in different context and areas for them to explore and gain more data about the relationship between the dependent variable which is customers satisfaction and customers loyalty and the independent variables such as tangibility, reliability, assurance, empathy, and responsiveness. Future researchers can also conduct the research in other locations, not only based in Shah Alam and future researcher may also conduct the research study in other target population and courier services in Malaysia and do a comparison towards PosLaju.

The data collection tool for this study was a questionnaire. Future researchers can combine other study approaches such as interviews to assess customers' satisfaction and loyalty to PosLaju courier service to achieve more reliable and precise data findings. As a result, the study will be able to obtain more precise data and more reliable results. The researcher may also be able to control their respondents to obtain more balanced results.

5.5 Conclusion

This section concludes the findings of this study which were guided by the objectives laid out in Chapter 1. Some of the study highlights showed that most respondents are satisfied with the customer service that PosLaju has provided. The respondents also feel that PosLaju has been able to match their expectations in delivering customer satisfaction. This study also highlights that most respondents also agreed that they would continue using PosLaju courier services. On the other hand, they also feel that they are loyal towards PosLaju. This research provides sufficient material and content to interpret customer satisfaction and customer loyalty on PosLaju courier service in Malaysia. In addition, this study also submits recommendations to future researchers on further improving and refining the results achieved in this study.

REFERENCES

- Ahmad, S. Z., Bakar, A. R. A., Faziharudean, T. M., & Zaki, K. A. M. (2015). An Empirical Study of Factors Affecting e-Commerce Adoption among Small- and Medium-Sized Enterprises in a Developing Country: Evidence from Malaysia. *Information Technology for Development*, 21(4), 555–572. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02681102.2014.899961>
- Akaegbu, J. B. (2013). An Exploratory Study of Customers' Perception of Pricing of Hotel Service Offerings in Calabar Metropolis, Cross River State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 4(11).
- Ali, F., Zhou, Y., Hussain, K., Nair, P. K., & Ragavan, N. A. (2016). Does higher education service quality effect student satisfaction, image and loyalty? A study of international students in Malaysian public universities. *Quality assurance in education*.
- Skinner, J., & Edwards, A. (2009). *Research methods for sport management*. Routledge.
- del Alonso-Almeida, M. M., Bagur-Femenías, L., & Llach, J. (2015). The adoption of quality management practices and their impact on business performance in small service companies: the case of Spanish travel agencies. *Service Business*, 9(1), 57-75.
- Alzaydi, Z. M., Al-Hajla, A., Nguyen, B., & Jayawardhena, C. (2018). A review of service quality and service delivery. *Business Process Management Journal*, 24(1), 295–328. <https://doi.org/10.1108/bpmj-09-2016-0185>
- Araim, M., Campbell, M., Cooper, C., & Lancaster, G. (2010). What is a pilot or feasibility study? A review of current practice and editorial policy. *What Is a Pilot or Feasibility Study? A Review of Current Practice and Editorial Policy*, 1–7. <https://bmcmmedresmethodol.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/1471-2288-10-67>
- Arlen, C. (2008). The 5 service dimensions all customers care about. *Service Performance Inc*, 10-15. <https://www.serviceperformance.com/the-5-service-dimensions-all-customers-care-about/>
- Ayub, A. H., Nik Muhammad Naziman, Y. H., & Samat, M. F. (2018). Factors influencing young consumers' purchase intention of organic food product. *Advances in Business Research International Journal (ABRIJ)*, 4(1), 17-26.
- Batra, M. M. (2017). Human sigma: What, why and why not. *Journal of Organizational Psychology*, 17(3), 40-51.
- Bernazzani, S. (2021, January 24). *Customer Loyalty: The Ultimate Guide*. Customer Loyalty: The Ultimate Guide. <https://blog.hubspot.com/service/customer-loyalty>
- Brightman, B. K. (2000). Reinforcing professional self-management for improved service quality. *Managing Service Quality: An International Journal*, 10(5), 299–306. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09604520010349179>

- Bryant, J. (2020, January 29). *How Reliable is Your Courier Service? | Orbit Same Day Richmond Virginia*. Orbit Same Day. <https://csiship.com/2019/12/17/how-reliable-is-your-courier-service/>
- Budianto, A. (2019). Customer loyalty: quality of service. *Journal of management review*, 3(1), 299-305.
- Chambers, S., & Chambers, S. (2020b, November 23). *The Importance of Customer Loyalty*. Customer Happiness. <https://www.nicereply.com/the-importance-of-customer-loyalty/>
- Chicu, D., Pàmies, M. del M., Ryan, G., & Cross, C. (2019). Exploring the influence of the human factor on customer satisfaction in call centres. *BRQ Business Research Quarterly*, 22(2), 83–95. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.brq.2018.08.004>.
- Firend, A. R., & Alvandi, S. (2015). Brand Awareness and Consumer Loyalty in Malaysia. *Research Journal of Social Sciences*, 8(6), 1-5.
- Gan, B. (2017). Executive summary of “Service characteristics’ impact on key service quality relationships: a meta-analysis”. *Journal of Services Marketing*, 28(4). <https://doi.org/10.1108/jsm-06-2014-0197>
- Gladly (2018). Customer Service Expectations Survey <https://cdn2.hubspot.net/hubfs/2771217/Content/2018%20Customer%20Service%20Expectations%20Gladly.pdf>
- Gulc, A. (2017). Models and methods of measuring the quality of logistic service. *Procedia Engineering*, 182, 255-264.
- Harlacher, J. (2016). An educator’s guide to questionnaire development. *Regional Educational Laboratory Central: Washington, DC, USA*, 108.
- Hennayake, H. M. G. Y. (2017). Impact of service quality on customer satisfaction of public sector commercial banks: A study on rural economic context. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 7(2), 156-161.
- Hill, N., & Brierley, J. (2017). *How to Measure Customer Satisfaction*. Taylor & Francis.
- Ho, J., Deik, D., Tiffany, F., Kok, L., & Teh, T. (2012). Logistic Service Quality among Courier Services in Malaysia. *Logistic Service Quality among Courier Services in Malaysia*, 38, 113–117. <http://www.ipedr.com/vol38/023-ICEBI2012-A10013.pdf>
- Ismail, A., & Yunan, Y. M. (2016). Service quality as a predictor of customer satisfaction and customer loyalty. *LogForum*, 12(4), 269-283.
- Izzah, N., Rifai, D., & Yao, L. (2016). Relationship-courier partner logistics and e-commerce enterprises in malaysia: A review. *Indian Journal of Science and Technology*, 9(9), 1-10.
- Jade, B. (2017, December). *Service Quality | Boundless Marketing*. Service Quality. <https://courses.lumenlearning.com/boundless-marketing/chapter/service-quality/>
- Jain, N. K., Kamboj, S., Kumar, V., & Rahman, Z. (2018). Examining consumer-brand relationships on social media platforms. *Marketing Intelligence & Planning*.

- Jeun, S. T., & Park, B. K. (2018). A Study on the Effects of Dissatisfaction of the Users of Internet Shopping Malls on Shopping Attitude And Shopping Propensity in China-Focused on the Moderating Effect of Economy Benefit. *Management & Information Systems Review*, 37(2), 23-42.
- Johnston, M. P. (2017). Secondary data analysis: A method of which the time has come. *Qualitative and Quantitative Methods in Libraries*, 3(3), 619–626.
- Jones, M. A., Taylor, V. A., & Reynolds, K. E. (2014). The effect of requests for positive evaluations on customer satisfaction ratings. *Psychology & Marketing*, 31(3), 161-170.
- Khadka, K., & Maharjan, S. (2017). Customer satisfaction and customer loyalty: Case trivsel städtjänster (trivsel siivouspalvelut).
- Kaura, V., Prasad, C. S. D., & Sharma, S. (2015). Service quality, service convenience, price and fairness, customer loyalty, and the mediating role of customer satisfaction. *International journal of bank marketing*.
- Khamis, A. R. (2013). *An examination of the relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction on mobile broadband provider: the case of zantel, Zanzibar* (Doctoral dissertation, Mzumbe University).
- Kierczak, L. (2021, January 21). *Customer Satisfaction: Why It's Still Important in 2021*. Survicate. <https://survicate.com/customer-satisfaction/importance-customer-satisfaction/>
- Kim, W. H. (2017). The Impact of Online Reviews on Customer Satisfaction: An Application of the American Customer Satisfaction Index (ACSI). *International Journal of Tourism Management and Sciences*, 32(5), 65–78. <https://doi.org/10.21719/ijtms.32.5.4>
- Komal Pancholi & P.K. Singh. (2018). Service Quality in Post Office Saving Banks. *International Journal of Management Studies*, 14(8), 31–45. [http://dx.doi.org/10.18843/ijms/v5i1\(2\)/06](http://dx.doi.org/10.18843/ijms/v5i1(2)/06)
- Krejcie, R. V., & Morgan, D. W. (1970). Determining sample size for research activities. *Educational and psychological measurement*, 30(3), 607-610.
- Leong, L. Y., Hew, T. S., Lee, V. H., & Ooi, K. B. (2015). An SEM–artificial-neural-network analysis of the relationships between SERVPERF, customer satisfaction and loyalty among low-cost and full-service airline. *Expert systems with applications*, 42(19), 6620-6634.
- Levyda, L. (2017). Have the Guests Perceived Superior Value?. *Binus Business Review*, 8(3), 199-206.
- Li, B. (2002). *A study of critical factors of customer satisfaction in parcel delivery service*. The University of Nebraska-Lincoln.
- Lovelock, C. (1996). *Services Marketing*. Prentice Hall. Upper Saddle River. NJ.
- Lumen Learning. (2018). *The Gap Model of Service Quality | Retail Management*. The Gap Model of Service Quality. <https://courses.lumenlearning.com/wmopen-retailmanagement/chapter/the-gap-model-of-service-quality/>

- Ma, Madu, & Madhu. (2002). Analysis of Customer Loyalty through Total Quality Service, Customer Relationship Management, and Customer Satisfaction. *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE)*, 3(3). <https://doi.org/10.11591/ijere.v3i3.6191>
- Majlis Bandaraya Shah Alam. (2014). Demographic. Retrieved from http://www.mbsa.gov.my/en-my/infoshahalam/kenalishahalam/Pages/lokasi_demografi.aspx
- Malaysian Communications and Multimedia Commission. (2018). *Industry Performance Report 2018*.
- MALAYSIAN COMMUNICATIONS AND MULTIMEDIA COMMISSION. (2018). *Postal and Courier Services*. Postal and Courier Services. <https://www.mcmc.gov.my/en/sectors/postal-courier>
- Mentzer, J. T., Flint, D. J., & Hult, G. T. M. (2001). Logistics Service Quality as a Segment-Customized Process. *Journal of Marketing*, 65(4), 82–104. <https://doi.org/10.1509/jmkg.65.4.82.18390>
- Mittal, S., Gera, R. and Batra, D. K. (2015). An evaluation of an integrated perspective of perceived service quality for retail banking services in India. *International Journal of Bank Marketing*.
- Mlekwa, M. D. (2014). *The effect of price fairness and customer service On customer satisfaction The case of mobile phone users of Tanga city* (Doctoral dissertation, Mzumbe University).
- Mohd-Any, A. A., Mutum, D. S., Ghazali, E. M., & Mohamed-Zulkifli, L. (2019). To fly or not to fly? An empirical study of trust, post-recovery satisfaction and loyalty of Malaysia Airlines passengers. *Journal of Service Theory and Practice*.
- Mohiuddin, M., Al Mamun, A., Syed, F., Mehedi Masud, M., & Su, Z. (2018). Environmental knowledge, awareness, and business school students' intentions to purchase green vehicles in emerging countries. *Sustainability*, 10(5), 1534.
- Ngo, Vu Minh; Nguyen, H. H. (2016). The Relationship between Service Quality, Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty: An Investigation in Vietnamese Retail Banking Sector. *Journal of Competitiveness*, 8(2), 103-116
- Ninikas, G., Athanasopoulos, T., Zeimpekis, V., & Minis, I. (2014). Integrated planning in hybrid courier operations. *The International Journal of Logistics Management*.
- Njei, Z. (2018). Relationship Between Customer Satisfaction And Customer Loyalty.
- Hasnan, N., Noordin, A., & Osman, N. H. (2014). Six main innovation issues: A case of service innovation of postal and courier services in Malaysia. *Journal of Technology Management and Business*, 1(1).
- Noor, M. H. M. (n.d.). Pos Laju dah jadi pos lambat. *Harian Metro*. Retrieved from <https://www.hmetro.com.my/mutakhir/2019/11/520899/pos-laju-dah-jadi-pos-lambat>

- Nurbasari, A., & Harani, N. H. (2018). Influence of customer relationship marketing and satisfaction of customer loyalty (Case Study: In Bank CIMB Niaga Lembong in Bandung). *Economics*, 6(2), 98-107.
- Nyadzayo, M. W., & Khajehzadeh, S. (2016). The antecedents of customer loyalty: A moderated mediation model of customer relationship management quality and brand image. *Journal of retailing and consumer services*, 30, 262-270.
- Oliver, R. L. (1999). Whence consumer loyalty?. *Journal of marketing*, 63(4_suppl1), 33-44.
- Omar, M. S., Ariffin, H. F., & Ahmad, R. (2016). Service quality, customers' satisfaction and the moderating effects of gender: A study of Arabic restaurants. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 224, 384-392.
- Otsetova, A. (2017). RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN LOGISTICS SERVICE QUALITY, CUSTOMER SATISFACTION AND LOYALTY IN COURIER SERVICES INDUSTRY. *Management & Education/Upravlenie i Obrazovanie*, 13.
- Panda, T. K., & Das, S. (2014). The role of tangibility in service quality and its impact on external customer satisfaction: A comparative study of hospital and hospitality sectors. *IUP Journal of Marketing Management*, 13(4), 53.
- Pandey, S., & Chawla, D. (2018). Online customer experience (OCE) in clothing e-retail: exploring OCE dimensions and their impact on satisfaction and loyalty—does gender matter?. *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*..
- Parasuraman, A., Zeithaml, V. A., & Berry, L. L. (1985). A conceptual model of service quality and its implications for future research. *Journal of marketing*, 49(4), 41-50.
- Parasuraman, A., Zeithaml, V. A., & Berry, L. (1988). SERVQUAL: A multiple-item scale for measuring consumer perceptions of service quality. 1988, 64(1), 12-40.
- Zeithaml, V. A., Parasuraman, A., Berry, L. L., & Berry, L. L. (1990). *Delivering quality service: Balancing customer perceptions and expectations*. Simon and Schuster.
- Parten, M. B. (1950). *Surveys, Polls, and Samples: Practical Procedures*. New York: Harper and Bros.
- Patel, N. (2021, June 15). *Customer Satisfaction: Benefits, Examples & Importance*. Neil Patel. <https://neilpatel.com/benefits-and-importance-of-customer-satisfaction/>
- Pei, Y. (2013). *Does service quality and customer satisfaction effect customer loyalty? A case study of a Chinese electric appliance chain retailer*. Høgskolen i Molde-Vitenskapelig høgskole i logistikk.
- Phiri, M. A., & Mcwabe, T. (2013). Customers' expectations and perceptions of service quality: the case of pick n pay supermarket stores in Pietermaritzburg area, South Africa. *International Journal of Research in Social Sciences*, 3(1), 96-104.

- Podcast Research. (2017). *The Advantages of Using Simple Random Sample to Study Larger Populations*. Using Simple Random Sample to Study Larger Populations. <https://www.invest.com/ask/answers/042915/what-are-advantages-using-simple-random-sample-study-larger-population.asp>
- Quinlan, C., Babin, B., Carr, J., & Griffin, M. (2019). *Business research methods*. South Western Cengage.
- Rasheed, F. A., & Abadi, M. F. (2014). Impact of service quality, trust and perceived value on customer loyalty in Malaysia services industries. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, *164*, 298-304.
- Roslan, N. A. A., Wahab, E., & Abdullah, N. H. (2015). Service quality: A case study of logistics sector in Iskandar Malaysia using SERVQUAL model. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, *172*, 457-462.
- Roslan, A., Nor, N., & Wahab, E. (2015). Service quality: A case study using SERVQUAL model. *Advanced Science Letters*, *21*, 2159–2162. <https://doi.org/10.1166/asl.2015.6243>
- Russo, I., & Confente, I. (2017). Customer loyalty and supply chain management: Business-to-business customer loyalty analysis. In *Customer Loyalty and Supply Chain Management: Business-to-Business Customer Loyalty Analysis*. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315162829>
- Samen, A.A.A-E., Akroush, M.N. and Abu-Lail, B. N. (2013). ‘Mobile SERVQUAL: a comparative analysis of customers’ and managers’ perceptions’. *International Journal of Quality & Reliability Management*.
- Sekaran, U., & Bougie, R. (2016). *Research methods for business: A skill building approach*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Siali, F., Wen, A. W. S., & Hajazi, M. U. A. (2018). Booming of online shopping in Malaysia: Do customers satisfy with parcel delivery service. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, *8*(12), 415-436.
- SMEinfo. (2018). *SME Annual Report*. Retrieved from <http://www.smeinfo.com.my/publication/sme-annual-report?view=simplefilemanager&id=40>
- So, K. K. F., King, C., Sparks, B. A., & Wang, Y. (2016). The role of customer engagement in building consumer loyalty to tourism brands. *Journal of Travel Research*, *55*(1), 64-78.
- Srivastava, M., & Rai, A. K. (2014). An investigation into service quality–customer loyalty relationship: the moderating influences. *Decision*, *41*(1), 11-31.
- Stale, D. (2021, March 19). *Customer Loyalty: Definition, Examples, Tips - Definition*. What Is Customer Loyalty: Definition and Guide. <https://sendpulse.com/support/glossary/customer-loyalty#:~:text=Customer%20loyalty%20is%20a%20measure,customer%20receives%20from%20a%20business.>
- Steward, P. (2021, May). *Service Quality*. Marketing Management Journal. <https://mktngmanagement.blogspot.com/2012/06/service-quality.html>

- Taber, K. S. (2017). The Use of Cronbach's Alpha When Developing and Reporting Research Instruments in Science Education. *Research in Science Education*, 48(6), 1273–1296. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11165-016-9602-2>
- Tharanikaran, V., Sritharan, S., & Thusyanthy, V. (2017). Service quality and customer satisfaction in the electronic banking. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 12(4), 67-83.
- The Star Online. (2018, November 5). SME Corp Malaysia: Budget 2019 is very supportive of SMEs. *The Star Online*. Retrieved from <https://www.thestar.com.my/business/business-news/2018/11/05/sme-corp-malaysia-budget-2019-is-very-supportive-of-smes>
- Warnick, M. S. (2015). *Quantitative analysis: Education and experience effects upon emergency preparedness for special needs*. Capella University.
- Wilson, A., Zeithaml, V., Bitner, M. J., & Gremler, D. (2016). *Services marketing: integrating customer focus across the firm*. Singapore: McGraw-Hill.
- Wisniewski, M. (2012). Using SERVQUAL to assess customer satisfaction with public sector services. *Managing Service Quality: An International Journal*, 11(6), 380–388. <https://doi.org/10.1108/eum0000000006279>
- Wu, P. H., Huang, C. Y., & Chou, C. K. (2014). Service expectation, perceived service quality, and customer satisfaction in food and beverage industry. *International Journal of Organizational Innovation*, 7(1).
- Yoo, M., & Bai, B. (2013). Customer loyalty marketing research: A comparative approach between hospitality and business journals. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 33, 166-177.
- Yuen, K. F., & Thai, V. V. (2015). Service quality and customer satisfaction in liner shipping. *International Journal of Quality and Service Sciences*.
- Zeba, F., & Ganguli, S. (2016). Word-Of-Mouth, Trust, and Perceived Risk in Online Shopping. *International Journal of Information Systems in the Service Sector*, 8(4), 17–32. <https://doi.org/10.4018/ijjiss.2016100102>

APPENDICES

APPENDIX A

Survey Questionnaire

Greetings dear participants,

My name is Zulazmi Bin Zakiuddin, a student from Master in Customer Service Management Program, the Faculty of Business and Management, Universiti Teknologi MARA Shah Alam. I am conducting a survey as part of the requirements for my degree. The objective of my research study is to determine the relationship between courier service quality (CSQ) and customer satisfaction and loyalty in Malaysia, using PosLaju brand as the context. If you have experience using the courier services from PosLaju (Pos Malaysia) within the past 6 months, I am inviting you to participate in this research study by completing the attached survey.

The following survey will require only between 5 to 8 minutes to complete. Your participation in the survey is voluntary. Answers given will be kept strictly confidential and used for academic purposes only. If you choose to participate, please answer all questions as honestly as possible and submit completed survey promptly. I thank you for taking the time to assist me in my educational endeavour. Should you have any questions regarding this survey, please contact me or my supervisor at the numbers below.

Sincerely,

Zulazmi Bin Zakiuddin / Mobile phone: 011-51751-691

Dr. Mazzini Binti Muda / Mobile phone: 012-9151-964

Screening Question:

Have you used PosLaju courier services from Pos Malaysia within the past 6 months?

Yes – Proceed with the survey

No – No need to proceed. Thank you.

Section 1: Respondent Information

No.	Question	Please tick (✓) your answer
1.	Gender	<input type="checkbox"/> Male <input type="checkbox"/> Female
2.	Age	<input type="checkbox"/> 18 Years Old or below <input type="checkbox"/> 19 – 25 Years Old <input type="checkbox"/> 26 – 35 Years Old <input type="checkbox"/> 36 – 45 Years Old <input type="checkbox"/> 46 Years Old and above
3.	Race	<input type="checkbox"/> Malay <input type="checkbox"/> Chinese <input type="checkbox"/> Indian <input type="checkbox"/> Others (please specify)
4.	Highest Education Level	<input type="checkbox"/> SPM <input type="checkbox"/> STPM/Diploma <input type="checkbox"/> Bachelor’s Degree <input type="checkbox"/> Master <input type="checkbox"/> PhD <input type="checkbox"/> Others (please specify)

5.	Employment status	<input type="checkbox"/> Student <input type="checkbox"/> Government sector <input type="checkbox"/> Private sector <input type="checkbox"/> Retired <input type="checkbox"/> Self-employed <input type="checkbox"/> Others (please specify)
6.	Monthly income	<input type="checkbox"/> Less than RM 3,000 <input type="checkbox"/> RM 3,001- RM 5,000 <input type="checkbox"/> RM5,001- RM 7,000 <input type="checkbox"/> RM7,001- RM 9,000 <input type="checkbox"/> RM 9,001 and above
7.	Frequency of using PosLaju courier services	<input type="checkbox"/> Once a month <input type="checkbox"/> Twice a month <input type="checkbox"/> Others (please specify)
8.	Do you use other courier services brands?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No If yes, please identify which courier service. <input type="checkbox"/> DHL <input type="checkbox"/> GDex <input type="checkbox"/> Ninja Van <input type="checkbox"/> Others (please specify)

Section B: Perception on Courier Service Quality of PosLaju

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Somewhat Disagree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Somewhat Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree

CODE NO.	INSTRUCTION: Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements based on the scale given above.	SCALE						
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7
	Tangibility							
T1	PosLaju outlets have modern looking equipment.							
T2	PosLaju physical facilities are visually appealing.							
T3	PosLaju staff uniform appears neat.							
T4	Materials associated with the service are visually appealing.							
T5	PosLaju outlets have convenient business hours.							
	Reliability							
R1	PosLaju postmen are dependable.							
R2	If PosLaju promises to do something by a certain time, they do so.							
R3	PosLaju postmen deliver my parcel on time.							
R4	PosLaju ensures my parcel tracking status updated.							
R5	PosLaju informs by calling me when they reach my house to deliver the parcels.							
	Assurance							
A1	When customers have problems, PosLaju will solve the problems with kindness.							
A2	Customers feel that their parcels are in good hands with PosLaju.							
A3	PosLaju assures customers of their parcels' safety.							
A4	PosLaju promises on time service delivery.							

A5	PosLaju installs confidence in serving customers.							
	Empathy							
E1	PosLaju is caring in serving their customers.							
E2	PosLaju gives individual attention to customers.							
E3	PosLaju is aware of the customers' needs.							
E4	PosLaju's employees are easy to communicate with.							
E5	Customer service of PosLaju is always available for customers.							
	Responsiveness							
RE1	PosLaju provides prompt services to customers.							
RE2	PosLaju is ever ready to help customers.							
RE3	PosLaju always reply to query/question from customers.							
RE4	PosLaju cares about their customers							
RE5	PosLaju always delivers the right parcel to customers (no mixed-up).							

Section C: Satisfaction with PosLaju courier services.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Somewhat Disagree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Somewhat Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree

CODE NO.	INSTRUCTION: Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements based on the scale given above.	SCALE						
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7
CS1	I am satisfied with the safety of my parcel.							
CS2	I am satisfied with the condition of my parcel.							
CS3	I am happy with the postmen's attitude.							
CS4	The courier services of PosLaju met my expectation.							

CS5	I am satisfied with customer services provided by PosLaju.							
CS6	Overall, I am satisfied with PosLaju services.							

Section D: Loyalty towards PosLaju courier services.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Somewhat Disagree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Somewhat Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree

CODE NO.	INSTRUCTION: Please indicate your level of perception with Customer Loyalty to use the same courier service.	SCALE						
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7
CL1	I would continue using PosLaju courier service in the future.							
CL2	I would still choose PosLaju courier service even when there are other similar services available.							
CL3	I would choose PosLaju courier service even if they increase the price.							
CL4	I would recommend PosLaju courier service to other people.							
CL5	I think I am a loyal customer of PosLaju.							

Comments and suggestions for improving customer satisfaction & customer loyalty on courier service quality in Malaysia.

Thank you for your participation.

APPENDIX B

Normality Q-Q Plot

Tangibility

Assurance

Responsiveness

Empathy

Reliability

Customer Satisfaction

Customer Loyalty

APPENDIX C

Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Tangibility	376	2.00	7.00	5.6622	1.08932
Reliability	376	2.00	7.00	5.6814	1.13235
Assurance	376	1.00	7.00	5.7016	1.14663
Empathy	376	1.00	7.00	5.6840	1.18351
Responsiveness	376	1.00	7.00	5.7133	1.13769
Customer Satisfaction	376	1.33	7.00	5.8684	1.03567
Customer Loyalty	376	1.00	7.00	5.6739	1.24954
Valid N (listwise)	376				

Tangibility

Descriptive Statistics			
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Tangibility 1	376	5.57	1.265
Tangibility 2	376	5.61	1.217
Tangibility 3	376	5.74	1.115
Tangibility 4	376	5.68	1.157
Tangibility 5	376	5.70	1.136
Valid N (listwise)	376		

Reliability

Descriptive Statistics			
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Reliability 1	376	5.71	1.152
Reliability 2	376	5.63	1.250
Reliability 3	376	5.67	1.258
Reliability 4	376	5.74	1.194
Reliability 5	376	5.66	1.250
Valid N (listwise)	376		

Assurance

Descriptive Statistics			
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Assurance 1	376	5.64	1.242
Assurance 2	376	5.74	1.139
Assurance 3	376	5.73	1.155
Assurance 4	376	5.68	1.202
Assurance 5	376	5.72	1.205
Valid N (listwise)	376		

Empathy

Descriptive Statistics			
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Empathy 1	376	5.69	1.201
Empathy 2	376	5.65	1.235
Empathy 3	376	5.68	1.216
Empathy 4	376	5.71	1.197
Empathy 5	376	5.69	1.248
Valid N (listwise)	376		

Responsiveness

Descriptive Statistics			
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Responsiveness 1	376	5.68	1.216
Responsiveness 2	376	5.71	1.182
Responsiveness 3	376	5.72	1.202
Responsiveness 4	376	5.69	1.221
Responsiveness 5	376	5.78	1.113
Valid N (listwise)	376		

Customers Satisfaction

Descriptive Statistics			
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Customer Satisfaction 1	376	5.89	1.085
Customer Satisfaction 2	376	5.89	1.038
Customer Satisfaction 3	376	5.86	1.073
Customer Satisfaction 4	376	5.86	1.106
Customer Satisfaction 5	376	5.85	1.151
Customer Satisfaction 6	376	5.86	1.110
Valid N (listwise)	376		

Customers Loyalty

Descriptive Statistics			
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Customer Loyalty 1	376	5.85	1.125
Customer Loyalty 2	376	5.73	1.290
Customer Loyalty 3	376	5.40	1.470
Customer Loyalty 4	376	5.73	1.327
Customer Loyalty 5	376	5.65	1.417
Valid N (listwise)	376		

APPENDIX D

Article from the Harian Metro

'Pos Laju dah jadi pos lambat'

Mohd Husni Mohd Noor
mhusni@hmetro.com.my

PERSIDANGAN Dewan Rakyat. FOTO Hiasan

"POS Laju dah jadi 'pos lambat,'" kata Oscar Ling Chai Yew (PH-Dap) yang mengeluh mengenai tahap perkhidmatan kiriman barang, Pos Laju oleh Pos Malaysia Bhd di Sarawak yang didakwa tidak memuaskan.

Chai Yew berkata demikian ketika sesi perbahasan peringkat jawatankuasa Rang Undang-Undang (RUU) Perbekalan 2020 Kementerian Komunikasi dan Multimedia di sidang Dewan Rakyat, Kuala Lumpur, hari ini.

"Saya ingin menarik perhatian kementerian bahawa Pos Laju di Sarawak sekarang perkhidmatan mereka tidak begitu memuaskan kerana Pos Laju dah jadi 'pos lambat'.

"Bagi kiriman barang dari Semenanjung ke Sarawak... tiga hari, satu minggu tidak sampai... lebih satu minggu... hampir dua minggu baru sampai, khususnya di Sibu ini.

"Tolong diberi perhatian oleh kementerian untuk atasi masalah ini sekali gus menambah baik perkhidmatan Pos Laju di Sarawak," katanya.

Katanya, ini hal yang serius dan kementerian perlu fikir bagaimana untuk mengatasi masalah ini.

Disiarkan pada: November 26, 2019 @ 4:13pm

APPENDIX E

Article from the Digital News Asia

Pos Laju handles record 4.42mil parcels from online purchases during 11.11 sale

By Digital News Asia November 30, 2018

- Invested US\$11.7 million in expanding Integrated Parcel Centre in Shah Alam
- Pos Laju will have another IPC ready by the middle of next year

POS Laju, the courier arm of Pos Malaysia Bhd sorted and distributed a record breaking 4.42 million parcels from e-commerce purchases during the biggest online mega-sale on 11.11.

This broke the record set in 2017 when four million parcels were delivered from the 11.11 sale.

“There’s been a rapid increase in e-commerce activities and I am happy to say that Pos Malaysia is playing a big part in supporting Malaysia’s rapidly growing Digital Economy. The current strength is strongly indicative of the digital transformation occurring in the country as increasing number of Malaysians are embracing online shopping as a new way of life,” said Pos Malaysia group chief executive officer Syed Md Najib Syed Md Noor.

Prior to the record breaking spike, the highest volume of parcels ever distributed by Pos Laju from a single day of online shopping was the recent 1.91 million online purchases made in October 2018 during the 10.10 online sales. As a comparison, the 11.11 craze topped the 10.10 record by a 32% jump in volume of parcels handled.

Having anticipated the strong rise in e-commerce, Pos Malaysia strengthened its delivery network with a US\$11.7 million (RM49 million) investment into the expansion of its Integrated Parcel Centre (IPC), in Shah Alam which was completed in July this year and enabled a more than doubling of the processing capability and capacity of 300,000 items daily as compared to 112,000 items prior to the expansion.

But Pos Malaysia is not done investing. Anticipating much stronger e-commerce growth, Pos Laju will have another IPC ready to enable it to handle 500,000 items daily by the middle of next year. The timing of Pos Malaysia’s investments into its logistics network is well timed as the recently released Google-Temasek eEconomy SEA Report 2018 has revealed 2018 to be the inflection point for e-commerce in the region with value doubling from US\$10.9 billion in 2017 to US\$23.2 billion in 2018.

Even more exciting is the report’s prediction that the e-commerce market in the region will be worth US\$102 billion by 2025.

Pos Malaysia has every intention of being a major player and trusted partner to all e-commerce merchants in the region.

APPENDIX F

Article from the TheStar Online

 TheStar Pos Malaysia to investigate Pos Laju staff caught tossing parcels

Pos Malaysia to investigate Pos Laju staff caught tossing parcels

NATION

Wednesday, 30 May 2018
4:04 AM MYT

PETALING JAYA: Pos Malaysia Berhad has launched an internal investigation and issued stern warnings to the staff of its courier arm Pos Laju who were seen throwing parcels into a cage trolley in a video that has gone viral.

"We want to assure you, our customers and stakeholders, that this is not reflective of who we are, or of our values at Pos Malaysia," it said in a statement on Tuesday (May 29) night.

Pos Malaysia called the incident an "isolated" one, and assured customers that it has always enforced strict standard operating procedures and codes of conduct.

"However, in this unfortunate circumstance, we apologise for where we were not perfect and did not live up to your expectations.

"We know that we carry a huge responsibility for the nation and we strive to live up to these standards of the highest order," it added.

Pos Malaysia said that it will have regular checks in the future to ensure proper work processes are practised.

"We will launch internal engagements to understand how we can further improve on our processes and adherence to our service delivery standards," it said.

AUTHOR'S PROFILE

Zulazmi bin Zakiuddin completed his Master in Customer Service Management at the Faculty of Business and Management, Universiti Teknologi Mara. His research interest is in the area of consumer towards service management of services. He received his first degree in Advertising at the Faculty of Communication & Media Studies, Universiti Teknologi Mara, in November 2006 and a recipient of Dean's List Award. He starts his career with Top Glove Sdn Bhd in Marketing & Sales Department from 2006 until 2018. Being a frontline to the company as a marketing and salesperson serving international business motivates the interest to pursue customer service management fundamentals. Presently, he is working with CJ Century Logistics Sdn Bhd as Senior Manager of Business Development.

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